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 SURVEY

The Synergy Between Digital Twin, Machine Learning, and Control Technologies in Water Supply Systems: A Critical Literature Review

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ABSTRACT A Digital Twin is a novel technological paradigm that emulates a real-world system. It is composed of a physical entity, its virtual counterpart (also known as the Digital Model), and communication channels. Digital Twins have gained traction in several industrial sectors, including the water sector. Through real-time communications, the Digital Model is continuously updated to mirror reality. This ensures high fidelity in the representation of a hydraulic model and subsequent effective operations in the Water Supply System. Consequently, this has incentivized the sensory upgrade of water networks, increasing the complexity and volume of data, and highlighting the need for more advanced tools. This has led to the emergence of Smart Predictive Digital Twins, which enhance predictive and decision-making capabilities. This technological progression was incentivized by the popularization of Machine Learning, Control algorithms, and Decision Support Systems. Currently, the literature review on Smart Predictive Digital Twins applied to drinking water networks is limited. To address this gap, this work conducts three individual literature reviews on its main technologies, applied to drinking water networks: Digital Twins, Machine Learning, and Real-time Control & Decision Support Systems. This systematic literature review approach provides a comprehensive overview of the various sub-areas where these technologies are applied in drinking water networks. Several emerging trends and research gaps have been identified, and potential synergies have been suggested for the future application of these technologies. This paper not only presents empirical findings but also showcases how predictive and decision-making capabilities are enhanced by leveraging these emerging tools.

INDEX TERMS Digital twin, water supply system, machine learning, control algorithms, decision support system, smart predictive digital twin.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the emergence of the Digital Twin paradigm has shown promise, gaining traction in numerous industries.

The water sector, due to its complexity and importance in society, has also embraced this novel technological tool. Succinctly, a Digital Twin utilizes data from a specific object (i.e., physical entity) and continuously updates its virtual counterpart. This approach enables improved monitoring of the real-world object, potentially improving its decision-making capability through a human operator or automated decision-support tools. As shown in subsequent sections, the adoption of the Digital Twin technology for the operational management of Water Supply Systems (WSS) is still scarce. Despite its clear advantages, integrating this novel tool for managing WSS has limitations and challenges. Firstly, water drinking networks are a critical infrastructure. Hence, any new technological implementation must be approached with caution, and regulatory constraints may also be faced. In the specific case of Digital Twins, it is also necessary to upgrade the sensory infrastructure. Without an abundance in quantity and variety of data regarding the state of the water network, the Digital Twin will not achieve its maximum potential. However, this retrofitting of the network's hardware has an initial setup cost. Additionally, implementing a Digital Twin in a WSS requires advanced technical expertise, encompassing software development and hydraulic knowledge.

Integrating Machine Learning (ML) tools with the Digital Twin framework unlocks many functionalities and significantly expands its analytical capabilities. Given enough data (i.e., collected historical data or real-time streams of data), ML techniques could be implemented for numerous applications to improve the management of WSS. The range of applications spans from anomaly detection, such as identifying leaks, to predicting future states. The latter includes predicting hydraulic conditions in a given time horizon (e.g., to be used in a model predictive control algorithm), water demands forecast, or simply for virtual sensors (i.e., simulating hydraulic values in the WSS where real sensors are non-existent). Adding ML tools to Digital Twins enriches it with more accurate simulations and predictions, and substantially upgrades its utility. This enhancement, in turn, improves the effectiveness of control mechanisms and decision-making tools used in water management.

Another transformative potential of Digital Twins in WSS is the implementation of real-time control and Decision Support Systems (DSS) capabilities. Operational management of WSS can be broadly categorized as pressure regulation and minimization of operational costs. By employing these tools, the system can achieve enhanced reliability and more efficient utilization of its resources.

Exploring the integration of Digital Twins, ML tools, and real-time control and DSS provides a thorough understanding of how these technologies can be synergistically employed to enhance the operation of WSS. This diverse technological integration leads to the Smart Predictive Digital Twin paradigm.

Given the emergent nature of Smart Predictive Digital Twins, this work adopts a comprehensive and segmented

analysis. Individual literature reviews were conducted for Digital Twins, ML, and real-time control and DSS algorithms applied in WSS. This approach ensures a thorough understanding of how each technology contributes to managing WSS and its synergistic potential with the Smart Predictive Digital Twin paradigm.

Moreover, this work aims to answer three fundamental research questions related to the Smart Predictive Digital Twins' technologies. These are addressed using both a quantitative and qualitative assessment derived from this multi-faceted literature review:

- **RQ1** - In the literature, is there any system built that could be considered a full implementation of a Smart Predictive Digital Twin?
- **RQ2** - What are the emerging trends (area of application or technology) in implementing Smart Predictive Digital Twins?
- **RQ3** - What are the limitations/challenges in the practical implementation of Smart Predictive Digital Twins in WSS?

The insights collected from this review methodology are expected to provide a technological direction for the development of Smart Predictive Digital Twins. Furthermore, the quantitative and qualitative assessments could provide information regarding the research gaps and technological trends in the several sub-fields.

II. MODERNIZATION AND MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES OF WATER SUPPLY SYSTEMS

WSS are essential infrastructures in human society, tasked with the continuous provision of safe drinking water to each corner of society. While the main objective is the uninterrupted delivery of water to consumers, this has to be done considering the infrastructure's health and the minimization of the wastage of resources (i.e., water and energy). It's worth highlighting that a similar proportion of energy is also wasted through leakage [1]. Furthermore, as noted in [2], that up to 50% of water resources within the European Union are lost, underscoring the need for a shift towards sustainable practices. Proper management of WSS needs to consider the following interconnected facets of these systems: water pressure throughout the network, water quality, equipment wear and tear, pump operation (also known as the Pump Scheduling Problem (PSP)), and respect for other hydraulic constraints. Furthermore, the increasing modernization of WSS has given rise to other novel issues, such as cybersecurity threats.

In order to maintain the health of the WSS's physical infrastructure, appropriate pressure ranges must be maintained throughout the network. High pressure can cause leakage and pipe bursts, while low pressure can cause dissatisfaction among consumers. Typically, for large water networks, District Metered Areas (DMA) are designed to ease pressure management. Given the vital role of WSS, their continuous operation leads to quick aging of components, i.e., wear and tear. This degradation in hardware happens not

only to the pipes but also to other critical components such as pumps, valves, and sensors. Thus, it is imperative to perform scheduled maintenance to avoid faults that compromise the effective functioning of the infrastructure. Unfortunately, manually verifying the conditions of every single component is expensive. Manual assessment of healthy components represents a misallocation of resources and also diverts attention from those nearing a fault. On the other hand, a late response to a faulty/malfunctioning component will lead to suboptimal operation of the network and monetary costs. Regulating the water quality is another crucial factor in managing a WSS, without which the system would not be usable by day-to-day consumers. The water quality within the network is ensured through continuous monitoring, the strategic addition of chemicals, and the prevention of water stagnation.

After securing the integrity of the physical infrastructure and the water quality, the subsequent imperative is to enhance the operational efficiency of these systems. This efficiency refers to reducing costs and minimization of resource wastage. In modern times, growing water scarcity and an increase in energy price volatility have pushed for more sustainable management practices. Moreover, WSS typically have limited investment, which motivates more efficient practices. As hinted, the goal of the operation of a WSS (solution of the PSP) is to efficiently operate pumps or valves in order to provide water to consumers while respecting hydraulic constraints (e.g., allowed pressure and water tank levels) and pursuing a certain objective, often minimization of costs. Very often, the water tank levels and energy prices are leveraged to minimize the cost of operation. This interconnection between the WSS and energy systems is typically known as the water-energy nexus. This paradigm can be approached from several perspectives, ranging from simply exploiting energy tariffs to the integration of devices that generate power that, hypothetically, could be sold back to the energy market. The potential of leveraging renewable energy sources such as wind and solar energy is emphasized in [3]. The benefits would be two-fold: mitigating environmental impact and reducing operational costs.

Several challenges hinder the robust and efficient management of WSS, including the design optimization of the physical infrastructure and/or the improvement of the operation methodologies. The former approach requires a careful consideration of environmental and anthropomorphic factors, which include the availability and demand for water resources, demography trends, and regional characteristics. While a collection of literature exists on optimization tools for the design of water networks, it is still a task dominated by experts. Usually, the design includes contingency measures to ensure the system's resilience against extreme situations, such as fires, floods, and pipe bursts. The devised redundancies, alongside potential poor designs, can lead to difficulties in effectively operating these systems. Besides designing water networks from the ground up, several other actions

can be taken to improve the efficiency of these systems, as detailed in [4]. These improvements range from retrofitting the network with new components (e.g., Variational Speed Pumps (VSP) and Pump as Turbines (PAT)) or partial redesign of the network. However, while potentially effective, these solutions can be overly costly to implement, and, consequently, the focus is often shifted to the optimization of operation strategies.

Improving the operations' management requires a low initial cost while being effective in reducing overall monetary expenditure. The PSP usually has a set of constraints that can be broadly categorized here as hydraulic, mechanical, or operational. Hydraulic constraints relate to the limits of components, such as the water tank's limit level, the allowable node pressure, and consumer demands. The mechanical constraints refer to rules that mitigate the wear and tear of components, particularly water pumps. For instance, to avoid excessive erosion, pump schedules are often designed to avoid frequent activation. Lastly, operation constraints refer specifically to the operation modes of pumps, which can be binary (on/off) or considering various speeds (i.e., varying degrees between 0 and 1), and the pump scheduling formulation itself (i.e., the mathematical formulation).

It becomes evident that effectively managing the WSS in all its dimensions requires an infrastructure capable of collecting, processing, and storing data, which is lacking in traditional WSS. This is due to inadequate investment in upgrading outdated water networks and a scarcity of experts capable of implementing a proper monitoring infrastructure. A monitoring system can upgrade operators' decision-making and alert them to immediate issues that might arise. The collection and processing of this data itself is invaluable and opens doors to more advanced techniques, such as ML predictive tools.

The water networks in WSS are usually complex and extend over a large geographic area to provide water to numerous consumers. While the placement of sensors is a valuable step to improve the WSS, they need to be strategically placed to be economically viable. Moreover, given the expansive nature of these networks, the choice of sensory technology plays a significant role. For instance, wireless sensors are likely more suitable than a wired network, offering a more practical and less intrusive method for system-wide integration. In recent times, Internet of Things (IoT) has emerged as a tool capable of overcoming this challenge. It consists of implementing a network of devices capable of real-time communication and autonomous data collection [5]. Usually, there is an emphasis on edge computing in this framework, which eases the overall processing of data. The sensors have to gather information and communicate in real-time with other entities (e.g., send data to operators or the information storing facility). Consequently, the data collected can/should be processed for further usage, e.g., pattern recognition. This falls into the

edge computing paradigm, potentially easing the computing burden of the overall system. Because of these requirements, the usage of smart meters has become popular, forming an Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI).

In practice, an advanced infrastructure acquires data from several sources throughout the network for long periods of time (or indefinitely). The management of this data, from its initial collection to its processing, requires the implementation of appropriate frameworks to ensure traceability. The necessities arise not only because of the several stages that the data goes through (e.g., collection, storage, analysis) but also due to its amount. Effective frameworks are essential to handle these complexities, ensuring the data remains manageable and usable.

Traditionally, WSS have relied on Supervisor Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems for monitoring and control of devices. Despite being introduced half a century ago, these systems continue to be integrated into modern framework proposals as an essential element (e.g., [6]). Even so, modern practices in Big Data need to be applied to handle not only the sheer amount of data but also the data interoperability. This essentially transforms the WSS into Smart Water Grids. In this paradigm a higher degree of monitoring and control throughout the whole water network is available. Recently, there has been an emergence of comprehensive systems (e.g., [7]) that leverage these technological advancements to improve monitoring and control over the network.

III. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW METHODOLOGY

A. INITIAL COLLECTION AND MANUAL FILTERING

This work focuses on the review of Digital Twins used in the management of WSS, including two of its core technologies: ML and Control/DSS algorithms. All research papers were collected from the Scopus and IEEE Xplore databases at the end of 2023. The queries used for each one of the topics are presented in Table 1. The utilization of Digital Twins in WSS is a relatively recent research topic that is gaining traction, but there are still very few publications on it. In contrast, there is a considerable amount of literature on both ML tools and control algorithms in WSS. Hence, to maximize the number of retrieved research documents for Digital Twins and minimize it for the remaining topics, a lenient query and more specific queries were applied, respectively. In general, in the queries' subsequent filtering stages, there was an effort to collect literature focusing on managing exclusively drinking water networks as a whole. More keywords could have been added to the presented queries for a more complete perspective of each technology's "ecosystem" regarding the management of WSS, but this would make the review task insurmountable. After filtering, the remaining documents were considered numerous enough to be considered comprehensive.

After collecting the body of the literature for each topic, three filtering stages were applied: removing duplicates,

abstract filtering, and manual filtering. Abstract filtering involves the removal of research papers by realizing a superficial analysis through the reading of the abstract, a process also henceforth referred to as "automatic filtering". In essence, this initial filtering aims to remove research literature that the query should have removed. Following this, a more in-depth filtering is conducted by a detailed examination of the research papers, which is called "manual filtering". Each topic has its own nuanced filtering process, which is elaborated next. Table 2 presents the number of documents filtered out and that remained after the overall filtering process.

Each review was conducted independently to gain a comprehensive understanding of each topic's overall popularity and trends within the WSS domain. Nevertheless, subsequent discussions consider these reviews both in isolation and contextualized with the global information so as to provide an inter-relationship analysis of the presented technologies. Due to the nature of each topic, somewhat different policies were adopted for the filtering process (mainly manual filtering) of each review, and thus, each has its own limitations. However, it's important to acknowledge that the valuable insights gained outweigh any limitations in the review process.

Firstly, regarding the Digital Twin review, there was some tolerance when performing the manual filtering. The emergence of Digital Twins in WSS is very recent, and there are a limited number of practical implementations. The manual filtering for the Digital Twins was simple, removing other sectors in the water sector, such as water treatment, irrigation, and wastewater management. Some works lacked a full bidirectional communication system and, therefore, could be considered Digital Shadows, but they were still selected in this review if the authors referred to them as Digital Twin. An additional critical factor is selecting research works that focus on the water network as a whole. Digital Twins built upon individual components (e.g., building a Digital Twin specifically for a water pump station) were removed.

The two remaining reviews broadly share the same filtering process, differing evidently on the topic in focus and the application in water networks as a whole. These reviews have a less relaxed filtering approach, removing any work that isn't clearly explicit about the implemented ML model or control/DSS algorithm. There is an exception to this rule, which is the implementation in big projects (e.g., Digital Twins). The review regarding Control and DSS clearly shows a great disparity of manually filtered compared to the other topics (see Table 2). Firstly, in the literature body, many works presented control algorithms applied to pumping systems in other contexts besides drinking water networks, which this work considered out of scope. Additionally, many works present control algorithms applied to pumps without considering the overall network, which is also considered out of scope in this work.

TABLE 1. Queries used for each of the reviewed topics.

Topic	Query
Digital Twin	"Digital Twin*" AND ("water supply" OR "water distribution" OR "water management" OR "water pump*" OR "water operat*") AND NOT ("drainage" OR "wastewater" OR "watershed" OR "sewer")
Machine Learning	"machine learning" AND ("water supply network" OR "water distribution network" OR "smart water grid" OR "water network" OR "water pump*" OR "water operat*" OR "water schedul*") AND NOT ("agriculture" OR "reservoir" OR "drainage" OR "wastewater" OR "watershed" OR "sewer" OR "groundwater" OR "freshwater" OR "irrigation" OR "farming" OR "runoff" OR "heating" OR "evapotranspiration" OR "rain*" OR "river" OR "basin" OR "lake" OR "coastal" OR ("water quality" OR "water treatment" OR "fungi" OR "contaminant*" OR "pollutant*"))
Control	("real time" OR "real-time") AND ("control" OR "decision support") AND ("water supply network" OR "water distribution network" OR "smart water grid" OR "water network" OR "water pump*" OR "water operat*" OR "pump schedul*") AND NOT ("agriculture" OR "reservoir" OR "drainage" OR "wastewater" OR "watershed" OR "sewer" OR "groundwater" OR "freshwater" OR "irrigation" OR "farming" OR "runoff" OR "heating" OR "evapotranspiration" OR "rain*" OR "river" OR "basin" OR "lake" OR "coastal" OR ("water quality" OR "water treatment" OR "fungi" OR "contaminant*" OR "pollutant*"))

TABLE 2. Filtering process for each review topic. Number of papers by review topic and by stage of collection/filtering.

Topic	Scopus	IEEE xplore	Total	After Removed Duplicates	After Abstract Filtering	After Manual Filtering
Digital Twin	97	29	126	115	40	29
Machine Learning	256	69	325	289	167	145
Control/DSS	318	125	443	397	88	75

B. QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF OVERALL RESEARCH PAPERS

The three chosen topics encompass the technologies underpinning Smart Predictive Digital Twins. Analyzing their respective popularity and trends provides insights into the future trajectory and allows for an understanding of the synergy between technologies. All data visualized and discussed in the following sections are derived from works present in the tables provided in the Annex or Table 3 (list of reviews). These tables are part of the review on Digital Twins (Table 11), ML (Tables 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, and 15) and Real-time Control & Decision Support Systems (Tables 16 and 17).

Fig. 1 presents publications on each topic over the years. Despite the gradual growth of publications, the Control/DSS topic has experienced a consistent pace. Given the foundational role of control algorithms in the operation of WSS, it is unsurprising that this topic has a substantial body of literature in the earliest years compared with the other reviewed topics. Visually, it is evident that ML has had a surge in popularity in the last few years. This technological dominance in the management of WSS can be traced to the overwhelming variety of ML tools and their capability to tackle a diverse number of tasks. Of the reviewed topics, Digital Twins is the most recent; thus, it has the least number of publications but has gained exponential growth in recent years.

The number of publications per topic might not be an appropriate measure of popularity. Fig. 2 complements Fig. 1 by allowing the visualization of the yearly density distribution of citations per year. In essence, utilizing only the number of citations for each research work would create a temporal bias in the data analysis because the most recent papers

would inherently have fewer citations due to the short time that publication has been available to read. To mitigate this temporal bias, the number of citations for each paper was divided by the age of the paper. Subsequently, a box plot was drawn for each year and topic to showcase the citations per year. The data necessary to construct this figure was acquired in the middle of 2024 (approximately at the beginning of July).

The best approach to analyze Fig. 2 is in a comparative manner, i.e., between topics. For instance, although the ML topic has the highest number of publications, it has shown the least citations per year in recent years, indicative of a saturated field. In contrast, although Digital Twins has the least number of publications, it possesses, in general, the highest number of citations per year compared to the other topics. This highlights that, besides a growth in publications, there is also a growth in interest in the field. While the field of ML seems to be over-saturated, it has a high level of maturity indicated by the high amount of review/discussion publications (see Table 3).

During this literature review, it was observed a lack of intersection between the selected topics (as illustrated by Fig. 3). This can be indicative of a general lack of maturity in terms of technological advancements in the WSS infrastructures. A more in-depth analysis of each publication reveals a broader overlap between the queried technologies than was initially indicated.

IV. DIGITAL TWINS TECHNOLOGY FOR DRINKING WATER NETWORKS

A. DEFINITION AND TECHNOLOGIES

Although the Digital Twin concept has become popular in many sectors, its formal definition is still being debated.

FIGURE 1. Temporal distribution of research work by literature topic over the years.

FIGURE 2. Density of citations per year, per literature review topic, over time.

In this subsection, the discussion centers on the many aspects regarding the definition of Digital Twin, not only to enlighten the reader but also to facilitate critical discussion of specific developed systems and respective technologies. Additionally, there is an attempt to define the minimum requirements for a Digital Twin system. This is done not as a formal definition proposal but as a way to aid further discussions.

The first concept of Digital Twin is typically associated with Product Lifecycle Management [21]. It had several names, such as the “Mirrored Spaces Model” and the

“Information Mirroring Model”, until NASA coined the name “Digital Twin” on its 2010 technology roadmap [22]. Afterward, Digital Twins’ popularity gained traction with the emergence of Industry 4.0. This revolution focused on increasing communication interconnectivity using concepts such as IoT and Big Data. Consequently, this made the practical implementation of Digital Twins in real-world scenarios more palpable. Nevertheless, this increase in popularity has also led to its adoption by many other sectors that saw it as a promising tool. However, this complicated the

TABLE 3. Number of review/discussion research work in each literature review.

	Citation	Title
Digital Twin	[8]	Digital Twins for Water Distribution Systems
	[9]	Digital Twin for Water Distribution Systems Management-Towards a Paradigm Shift
ML	[10]	A Literature Review on Machine Learning to Optimize Water Network Management Using Natural Language Processing
	[11]	A Review on Current Technologies and Future Direction of Water Leakage Detection in Water Distribution Network
	[12]	An evolution of statistical pipe failure models for drinking water networks: a targeted review
	[13]	Artificial intelligence for the modeling of water pipes deterioration mechanisms
	[14]	Models and explanatory variables in modelling failure for drinking water pipes to support asset management: a mixed literature review
	[15]	The challenges of predicting pipe failures in clean water networks: a view from current practice
	[16]	Toward Sustainable Water Infrastructure: The State-Of-The-Art for Modeling the Failure Probability of Water Pipes
	[17]	Trends and applications of machine learning in water supply networks management
	[18]	Uncertainties in different leak localization methods for water distribution networks: a review
[19]	Water pipe failure prediction and risk models: state-of-the-art review	
Control/ DSS	[3]	A review of operational control strategies in water supply systems for energy and cost efficiency
	[20]	Real time control of water distribution networks: A state-of-the-art review

FIGURE 3. Intersection of publications in the topics of digital twin, ML, and real-time control and decision support.

definition of Digital Twins, given that each domain has its own needs, problems, and technological tools.

A Digital Twin was first conceived in [21] as a framework with three components: the physical system’s sensors/information, its virtual representation known as the Digital Model, and the connection that allows the flow of information between these components. The initial premise was to create a feedback loop of information through a bi-directional channel, continuously updating the physical entity and the virtual counterpart with the latest information. In the literature, the real-world system or process is commonly

known as the “Physical Entity” or “Physical Twin” [23]. Similarly, the corresponding virtual counterpart is often referred to as the “Virtual Twin” or “Digital Model”. Additionally, the act of exchanging information between the Physical Twin and the Virtual Twin for the purpose of synchronizing states and actions is known as “Twinning,” and the rate of update is the “Twinning rate”.

Some core concepts, such as “Digital Model”, “Digital Shadow”, and the “Digital Twin” itself, are still being scrutinized. The work in [24] categorizes the existent Digital Twins based on their data integration. In this paradigm, the Digital Model is viewed as a standalone module where the exchange of information happens manually or through the use of external mechanisms. In this categorization, the Digital Model is considered to have the lowest integration of data since the flow of information happens manually in all instances. Moving beyond this starting point, the next level would be the Digital Shadow, in which an automatic data flow is added from the Physical Twin to the Digital Model. However, the information flow from the Digital Model and the Physical Twin would still happen manually. Finally, the last layer of data integration would be the Digital Twin, ensuring an automatic bi-directional flow of information. While this categorization elucidates these core concepts individually, it is argued in the work [25] that this might obscure terminologies, given that from this perspective, a Digital Model is still a Digital Twin, just with less data integration. For clarity, this work adopts the previous definitions of Digital Model, Digital Shadow, and Digital Twin, without the hierarchical structure.

Numerous instances in the literature exist where these latter core terminologies are broadly used or wrongly presented. For instance, the system proposed in [26] presents an architecture exhibiting the typical properties indicative of a Digital Twin, e.g., the existence of a Digital Model, at least one direction flow of information, and data storage. However, the mentioned “Digital Twin” seems to actually be referring to a “Digital Model”. This overlooks the fact that the overall system could potentially be considered a Digital Twin when adopting a more relaxed definition. Another example would be the frequent use of the term “Digital Shadows” in the literature as a synonym (or very similar) for “Digital Twins” [25].

Evidently, a lack of a universal formal definition of Digital Twins hinders progress in academia and industry. A clear set of categorization criteria must be defined to address this issue. In the literature, there are numerous reviews that discuss the definition, aspects and categories of Digital Twins (e.g., [23], [24], [27], [28], [29], and [30]). In an effort to find common ground, some meta-reviews on the subject have been published (e.g., [25] and [31]). When reviewing the literature, a notable disparity of requirements is evident throughout the several domains. This has led to a growing list of requirements for a system to be considered a Digital Twin, as highlighted in [30]. Henceforth, this discussion is concluded by outlining what could potentially be considered strictly necessary requirements for a Digital Twin system.

The existence of a virtual representation is generally accepted as a required property for a Digital Twin [25]. However, the level of fidelity, scale, and number of Digital Models should, in turn, be domain-specific in order to achieve a universal consensus.

There is an ongoing debate in the literature on whether the connection between the Physical Twin and the Digital Model should be bi-directional and automatic. Traditionally, the Digital Twin's information flow has been viewed as a feedback loop, where the information flow from the Physical Twin would be used to update the Digital Model to the latest state. Consequently, the most up-to-date control data would then be sent back. Firstly, the bi-directional nature of the exchange of information has somewhat of a consensus in the literature [25]. Secondly, the work in [23] argues that if the virtual-to-physical connection doesn't exist, it is then difficult to distinguish the system from a simulator that received an instance of the Physical Twin's state. This puts into question "Digital Twins" used for the purpose of optimizing the design of infrastructures. The criticism stems from the fact that, despite receiving data, these systems produce outputs only at the user's discretion rather than operating within a continuous feedback loop. Even with some leniency, the lack of dynamic real-time information exchange raises the question of whether these systems resemble simulators more than Digital Twins.

In contrast, it is argued in [32] that a Digital Twin that directly controls the Physical Twin is considered misleading. Specifically, if the well-functioning of the physical entity is dependent or augmented by generated controls, then the system would technically be considered a Cyber-Physical System (CPS). Additionally, there are security concerns about automatically sending controls to a critical system.

In summary, it can be argued that a Digital Twin should possess continuous communication between components. However, these communication interactions should be set up in a way that does not compromise the independence of the physical system. It is out of the scope of this work to elaborate on what this entails, but broadly, a hypothesis could be having a Digital Twin receiving continuous data from the physical twin and sending back control data, passing first through an intermediary (e.g., the CPS).

Finally, a Digital Twin could have numerous tools, depending on the final application of the system. Some works (e.g., [33]), implement an extra component besides the Physical Twin and Digital Model, referred as services. Services are simply the group of analytical tools that the Digital Twin possesses and frequently leverages the Digital Model for outputting future predictions or what-if scenarios. This framework is implicitly considered in the rest of the document.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW OF DIGITAL TWINS IN WSS

The literature on the application of Digital Twins in WSS is scarce and predominantly dominated by

"Proof-Of-Concepts" rather than real-world on-site applications. In order to understand the level of maturity in this specific field, an attempt was made to classify the Digital Twins based on their level of technological maturity. Specifically, the aim was to find works that apply a proof-of-concept application in a real-world context and include real-time communications. Only the work in [34] fits this description, focusing on leak detection. Other works applied to real-world settings were found, such as those in [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40], [41], and [42], but are more directed towards planning/designing tasks, not involving real-time communications. An important observation here is that the works in [37], [38], [39], [40], and [41], are based on the same ongoing Digital Twin system. Although most other works focus on showcasing a proof-of-concept, some try to simulate the use of communication technology. A notable example of this case is the work in [43], which aims to integrate streaming data for real-time simulations. Another example is presented in [44], which applies blockchain technology to validate data across several nodes. It's worth mentioning that implementing a Digital Twin with continuous communication with the real physical entity holds a multitude of issues, such as needing expert personal and financial investment for the development of the actual communication system, security issues, and economic uncertainty of the payoff of implementing such a system. The literature review also found research works that propose frameworks but do not follow a pragmatic application (e.g., [45] and [46]). These works were included due to their potential insights.

As stated earlier, one of the most crucial components of the Digital Twin is the Digital Model, which is responsible for emulating several aspects of the physical entity. The EPANET hydraulic simulator was the most predominantly used Digital Model (Fig. 4). There was an expectancy to find an abundance of research works that used ML models as Digital Models, but only four were found: [36], [47], [48], and [49]. This highlights the lack of maturity either from the Digital Twin or ML domains. It is crucial to note that the categorization of the digital representation wasn't always straightforward. For instance, in the work in [47], both EPANET and a Graph Neural Network (GNN) model were employed for the system's state estimation. As a result, in this aforementioned work, the digital model was categorized both as EPANET-based and ML-based in Fig. 4.

Due to the multifaceted nature of the Digital Twins, each one can have several functionalities, and these range from simple Hydraulic State Estimators (e.g., [47], [50]) to fault prediction (e.g., [48]). As can be seen in Fig. 5, the task of leak localization was the most explored one (e.g., [49], [51], [52]), which underscores its importance in the management of WSS. One of the most promising features of Digital Twins is its capability to realize network analysis in a number of different scenarios. A notable example of this is the work in [53], which investigates water demands' effects on the water network. It's worth pointing out that even though

FIGURE 4. Distribution of types of digital models found in digital twin applications.

Digital Twins were found that had a control task, only one focused on control for economic gains [54], specifically the generation of energy with PAT. All other works in the control category focus mainly on pressure regulation, analyzing how several control configurations can affect the efficiency of the WSS’s operation (e.g., [42]), or using these controls to assess if a design of a network/DMA can regulate pressures properly (e.g., [40]).

In the literature review, it was found a surprising amount of Digital Twins that focused on Anomaly and Attack Detection (e.g., [55], [56], [57], [58], [59], and [60]). These works focus mainly on anomaly detection in the data transmitted to and from the WSS. These Digital Twins often work as an intermediary component of a CPS, where the hydraulic model is used to predict and consequently compare its outputs with real data to detect anomalies. The work in [59] additionally includes a communication network, adding robustness to threat models.

C. COMMERCIAL REVIEW OF DIGITAL TWINS IN WSS

The development of a Digital Twin is a highly complex task and requires multidisciplinary experts alongside financial investment. This could explain the overabundance of Digital Twins’ proofs-of-concept rather than of “full-fledged” implementations until this point. To complement the academic literature review presented a commercial review was also conducted. The Google search engine was utilized for the commercial review with the use of the following query: “digital twins” AND “water supply systems” AND (“application” OR “case study” OR “commercial”). Digital Twins are a novel technology with great potential to affect numerous industries, but, as seen previously, its definition can be broad. It can be argued that “Digital Twin” has become somewhat of a buzzword. This makes the commercial review susceptible to marketing influences, which can oversell the capabilities of the product/services. To mitigate this issue

TABLE 4. Digital Twins implementations found in the commercial review.

Organization	Functionalities (Keywords)	Type	Pilot
[62]	Planning, What-if scenario, Monitor, Anomaly Detection	Product	Manaus’ São Jorge District (Brazil), District of Columbia (United States of America)(USA)
[63]	Decision Support, Predictive Maintenance, Monitor, What-if Scenario	Service	Linköping (Sweden), Toronto and York region (Canada)
[64]	What-if scenario, Monitor, Predictive Control, Leak Detection	Service	Not mentioned
[65]	Planning, Operation, Leak Detection	Service	Goulburn-Murray Water (Australia)
[66]	Monitor, Operation	Product	Not mentioned
[67]	Monitor, Demand Prediction, Operation	Service	Curitiba (Brazil), Cantanhede and Ronqueira (Portugal)
[68]	Predictive Maintenance, Monitor, Operation, Design, Planning	Product	Wellington, New Zeland
[69]	Leak Detection, What-if scenario, Design, Operation	Service	Not mentioned
[70]	Planning, Leak Detection, Simulations	Service	Not mentioned
[71]	Leak Detection, Operation (hinted)	Product /Service	Not mentioned

during the collection of Digital Twins examples, a set of criteria was defined. First of all, the term “Digital Twin” should be mentioned anywhere on the organization’s website. This, unfortunately, can filter out systems that, although they don’t explicitly mention Digital Twins, the showcased technology could be classified as such. Additionally, it was only considered systems that mention, or at least hint, at including hydraulic modeling and communication systems in the presented software. Only Digital Twins encompassing the WSS system as a whole were included. Digital Twins that focused on standalone components were not included. A notable example is the Digital Twin developed by Siemens [61] to manage pump stations. Finally, organizations that weren’t explicit about the aforementioned characteristics were excluded. This has the disadvantage of potentially excluding noteworthy Digital Twins from the search but ensures all collected works are relevant. Considering the vast number of results with the selected search engine, only the top results were analyzed. While not exhaustive, this approach is deemed sufficient to provide an overview of the commercial landscape of Digital Twin technologies. Table 13 highlights the most pertinent Digital Twins found in the commercial review.

The closed-source nature of this commercial review does not allow the same methodological identification of Digital Twin systems as in the academic review. Instead, it requires relying on claims done by the vendors. The identified Digital Twins were categorized based on functionalities described on their respective organizations’ websites. A significant portion of these Digital Twins found had “Operation” and “Decision Support” functionalities, broadly representing the capability to effectively operate actuators in the WSS. “What-if scenario” was also publicized, suggesting the

FIGURE 5. Digital Twins' applications found in the literature.

integration of large-scale software with human operators. Many organizations offer Digital Twins as a service, while those providing it as a product include a comprehensive suite with multiple tools. This highlights the complexity in implementing Digital Twins tailored to specific use cases.

V. MACHINE LEARNING IN WATER SUPPLY SYSTEMS' OPERATIONS

A. OVERVIEW OF STATE-OF-THE-ART ON ML MODELS IN WSS

A significant limitation of this work lies in the initial collection of relevant literature. Despite employing a query to include all the relevant literature, ML papers proved to be particularly challenging. A query that was too broad (i.e., searching for every potential term used for "Machine Learning" models) would yield an insurmountable volume of papers for review, while the currently used query risked omitting some potentially relevant papers. Consequently, there is an anticipated bias against papers that employ ML models as hydraulic simulators because other terms, such as "surrogate models" and "metamodels", are often used interchangeably in the abstracts. The number of papers collected related to ML models is considered to be extensive enough for a proper discussion of trends. Furthermore, due to the innovative approach in this review, several papers detailing surrogate models are inherently included in this discussion due to the control algorithms literature review.

In this work, upon reviewing the collected research papers, it was decided to categorize each work in terms of the application of the ML tool in the WSS. Fig. 6 showcases the distribution of publications over the years, categorized by the application of the ML tools. It's worth specifying that the categories presented refer to the specific use case of the ML tool. Consider, for instance, a research paper with the purpose of detecting leaks; if the sole objective of the ML tool implemented is to predict future hydraulic states, then it would be categorized "Hydraulic state estimation" instead of "Leak detection and localization". This allows for a more ML-centric discussion.

While most defined categories are self-titled, it's worth elaborating exactly what ecosystem of papers is included in each. "Leak detection and localization" considers papers in which the corresponding ML tools detect leakage and potentially its respective location. Similarly, "Fault prediction" focuses on using ML tools for predicting future pipe breaks or even segmenting network regions in terms of probability of fault. While very similar, a nuance is needed to differentiate both. The leak detection category refers to the real-time prediction of leaks, normally using pressure data to find leak-like patterns, while fault prediction is more focused on predictive maintenance, hence the tools used are aimed at predicting pipe breaks in a bigger time frame. There is also a need for nuance when it comes to the "Anomaly and attack detection". It focuses mainly on anomaly detection of data from

sensory systems. ML tools in “Hydraulic state estimation”, as the name implies, focus on the prediction/estimation of hydraulic states. The “Water consumption forecast” category refers, as expected, to ML tools used to predict future water demands. In the “Direct Control” category, the ML tools output control configurations for the WSS, which can either implement Reinforcement Learning (RL) or rule-based control algorithms. “Data handling calibration” focuses mainly on treating data from the sensory infrastructure. This work also includes the category of “Network design” that, as the name suggests, focuses on implementing ML tools to design optimal network configurations. In this review, it was also considered other reviews/discussions picked up by the query. The objective of this analysis is to showcase and investigate potential gaps in knowledge in the application of ML tools in WSS. Finally, there is also the category of “Miscellaneous” papers that include ML tools used in ways not inserted in other categories. For instance, the work in [72] utilizes Federated Learning that focuses on the training of other ML models while incentivizing privacy and decentralization.

Fig. 6 indicates the emergence of ML tools in each category over the years. From a global perspective, it is visible that the use of ML started to gain traction around 2018, which is relatively recent. In the year 2020, the ML tools were prevalently applied to fault detection. Subsequently, it became predominantly utilized for leak detection and localization, surpassing the combined usage of these tools in any other category by the year 2023.

Several different ML tools were identified and further categorized from the selected research papers. Fig. 7 shows the evolution of each type of ML over the years. Before proceeding with the explanation of each one of the indicated categories it is worth mentioning that in the field of ML exists an extreme diversity of tools. Because of this, not only can some research papers have more than one different ML tool, but occasionally, the same model utilizes multiple concepts. For instance, the work in [73] uses a gradient boosting decision tree, making it able to fit both the “Tree based methods” and “Boosting” categories. Firstly, the “Tree based methods” category refers to ML models using decision trees, Random Forest (RF), or any other similar variations. “Boosting” is an umbrella category for ensemble methods. By definition, boosting methods rely on other ML tools, as they focus on improving the task by iteratively refining and combining these ML models. Using a category specifically for boosting techniques can potentially enrich the discussion. “Neural network based” encompasses all and any model that utilizes Neural Networks (NN), which includes Fully Connected Neural Networks, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), GNN, Autoencoders, and RL. The theoretical paradigm of RL does not view the use of NN as a necessary requirement. However, given the widespread adoption and significant success of integrating both concepts (also known as Deep

Reinforcement Learning (DRL)), it is regarded as relevant to categorize it within this last category. The “Statistical distribution approximators” category, in essence, includes ML techniques that use Gaussian, or Poisson distributions, and utilize other statistical approaches such as Bayesian methods. “Clustering methods/feature reduction” includes ML methods focusing on clustering and feature reduction, such as K-means and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The “Alternative kernel function approximations” category aims at grouping together all the remaining ML methods that focus on approximating specific functions, excluding statistical distributions and neural networks. This category includes linear regression, logistic regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Support Vector Regression (SVR), and other similar techniques. Finally, the “Other” category includes any other ML technique not included in the aforementioned categories, typically including rule-based ML techniques. The presented categories have been designed to include, in each, ML tools with similar properties or that exhibit similar behaviors. This allows for a more enriched discussion on the trends of ML.

Fig. 7 shows that until 2020, no ML tool category was definitively dominant, at which point tree-based methods surged to peak popularity. Subsequently, these methods had a decline in usage and were surpassed by NN, which had exponential growth in usage. A notable mention is the fact that while the alternative kernel function approximations had a smaller growth, these are still very popular. The number of publication that utilized tree-based methods peaked in 2020 and subsequently declined, surpassed by NN-based methods. This trend coincides with the shift of popularity from fault prediction to leak detection and localization applications, which occurred in the same year.

As evidenced by Fig. 8, each ML application category has a different distribution of these algorithms. This makes sense, considering that each application domain consists of different tasks (e.g., pattern recognition and prediction of next state). Only these three categories were included since they respected the arbitrary rule of accounting over 10% of the total number of research works. From the bar chart, it is observable that, in general, NN were popular in these domains. For both leak and fault detection “Tree based methods”, “Neural networks based”, and “Alternative kernel function approximators”, were the more popular ML techniques.

Each application domain has different characteristics that require a thoughtful selection of the appropriate ML tool. The most pertinent aspect when selecting the architecture is the size and quality of the dataset. This is often impacted by how the dataset was obtained, i.e., synthetically generated by a simulator, collected from real-world sensory infrastructures, or other historical data. The data collection within a specific application domain often dictates the selection of a suitable ML tool. For instance, in the case of leak detection, if the dataset was collected from actual real-world scenarios, it is reasonable to anticipate a small number of data points due

FIGURE 6. Distribution of ML Research Works in WSS by Category and their publication evolution.

FIGURE 7. Distribution of ML algorithms by Category and their publication over the years.

to the infrequent occurrence of leaks. Subsequently, a data-efficient ML tool needs to be selected, e.g., SVM.

Fig. 9 showcases the distribution of real-world, synthetically generated, and mixed datasets over several application

FIGURE 8. Distribution of ML tools by the categories applied for leak detection and location, Fault Prediction, and Hydraulic State Estimators.

domains. From a global perspective, datasets being collected from real-world scenarios are the most common. The “Water consumption forecasting” and “Fault prediction” categories have a disproportional amount of real-world datasets, the latter having only one paper with a synthetic dataset. This can be due to the difficulty of synthetically generating data of this nature. It is important to note that some synthetic datasets identified in the ML literature review are also present in the other reviews. Therefore, it is pertinent to briefly mention the most frequently used synthetic datasets throughout the overall review: Hanoi, Tnet1, Anytown, NET3, Bk-Town, Cherry Hill/Brushy plains, New York Tunnel, Fossolo, and Modena. Other specific water drinking networks are often used both to train/validate ML models and validate control algorithms, such as the ones in [74], [75], [76], [77], [78], [79], and [80]. Specific datasets are also tailored to particular applications. For the application of anomaly and attack detection, it is standard to utilize specialized datasets such as SWaT [81], WADI [82], and BATADAL [83], as well as other testbeds (e.g., [80]).

B. MAINTAINING NETWORK’S RELIABILITY

Given the popularity of the sub-fields of leak detection and fault prediction, with the addition of anomaly and attack detection, one can reasonably infer that maintaining physical integrity is the current top priority in the management of WSS. This makes sense, considering that a failure in a component can lead to a substantial waste of water and energy and, consequently, financial losses. A fault in a pump or pipe jeopardizes pre-established control routines that were finetuned to the network’s specific hydraulic behavior, incurring an indirect increase of costs. Additionally, if not quickly detected/resolved, these faults can potentially initiate cascading events that negatively affect other components.

A leak in a water network can occur due to several factors, such as the corrosive nature of the soil, water pressure, or external pressure caused by the terrain. Because the pipes are usually underground, detecting leaks can be cumbersome. Leak detection can be categorized in three main approaches [84]. The first relates to implementing specialized sensors, such as acoustic signal sensors, vibration sensors,

FIGURE 9. Distribution of the type of datasets in the categories of application.

or even MEMS-based sensors. Research works that utilize acoustic signals are exemplified in [85], [86], and [87]. One main downside of this first approach is the cost of installing these sensors in larger networks and the subsequent complexity of managing these sensors. For instance, the work in [88] addresses the energy expenditure of wireless acoustic sensors. The second method is a transient-based approach that essentially focuses on using transient flow data gathered from sensors and comparing it to analytical models of transient behaviors. Although effective, this method is not scalable to larger water networks. In this literature review, only one method was identified using this approach [89]. The last category refers to the typical modeling of the hydraulic behavior of the water network. Since these methods mostly utilize pressure/flow data collected over the network to construct a model, it is possible to repurpose already existing network sensors. This, in turn, makes this third approach cheaper to apply and easier to deploy. Table 5 categorizes the research on leak detection into two groups: sensor-based methods, which employ specialized sensors such as accelerometers or acoustic devices, and hydraulic-based methods, which typically rely on pressure and flow sensors to model the hydraulic behavior of the network.

The event of a leak is usually infrequent, potentially leading to imbalanced datasets, which hinders ML techniques. The work in [122] addresses this issue with domain adaptation techniques. Additionally, the sporadic nature of leaks creates the expectation of a scarcity of real-world datasets. However, that is not what was observed in

TABLE 5. References categorized by leak detection methodologies.

Category	References
Sensor-based	[85], [88], [90], [87], [86], [91], [92], [93], [94]
Hydraulic-based	[95], [96], [89], [97], [98], [99], [100], [101], [102], [103], [104], [105], [106], [107], [108], [109], [110], [111], [112], [113], [114], [115], [116], [117], [118], [119], [120], [121], [122], [84], [99], [100], [123], [101], [124], [125], [126], [127], [128]

this literature review. Apparently, the drive towards more sustainable and economically feasible WSS management has led to the production of works focusing on testing the performance of algorithms in real data. Some works, inclusively, create laboratory environments to test new methods (e.g., [94], [97], [113], [114], and [126]). This progressive abundance of real-world data also signifies a shift from data-efficient methodologies (e.g., SVM, Decision Trees) to high-consuming ones, i.e., Deep Learning (DL). Examples that leverage the latter paradigm are present in the works in [123], [124], [125], and [126], which implement NN models for leakage prediction/detection. There is an emergence of works that focus on detecting leaks and moving towards localization and size estimation. These methods are invaluable for quick response and priority assessment in handling damaged pipes.

A real-time detection of leaks is essential for the proper management of WSS since it allows for quick responses to these failures. Another approach that is equally valuable is

the prediction of future faults in these systems. As observed in the previous quantitative analysis, while losing traction in the last few years, it is still one of the most researched sub-fields for managing WSS. Prediction of faults is essential for an effective preventive rehabilitation or maintenance of the several components in the water network. Being able to foresee the component that probably will fail next not only prevents potential water wastage but also avoids dramatically affecting the normal functioning of the rest of the system.

The main difference between these two categories is that leak detection focuses on real-time detection of water leakage, while fault prediction aims to predict future failures in components. Considering the nature of the latter category, it is not surprising that most research works focus on the dominance of real-world datasets. In this review, the only work on fault prediction that had only a synthetic dataset focused mostly on optimal sensor placement [129]. Other works that used some sort of synthetic dataset, alongside a real-world one, either utilized a hydraulic model alongside historical data [130], utilized a hydraulic simulator to generate performance metrics [131], or enriched the dataset with generated faults [132].

In the developed methodologies, most fault prediction research works include data related to pipe attributes and corresponding historical data, i.e., previous faults in pipes. Only a few works include as input terrain quality (e.g., [133], [134], [135], [136], [137]), weather characteristics (e.g., [138], [139]), surrounding infrastructures that can cause disruptive vibrations (e.g., [131], [140], [141], [142]), and socio-demographic factors [73]. In this field, it is noticeable a very diverse amount of ML techniques. To name a few, there exists implementations of Decision Trees (e.g., [73], [142], [143]), RF (e.g., [128], [131], [139], [140], [144]), linear or logistic regressions (e.g., [145], [146]), Extreme Learning Machine [147], Dirichlet Mixture Model (e.g., [148], [149]), and finally NN (e.g., [146], [150], [151], [152], [153], [154]).

It is evident that a large body of research exists in the literature for detecting and predicting faulty components, including implementing advanced sensory infrastructure. However, many of the issues that might arise could potentially be mitigated at an earlier stage through the optimal design of the water network.

Relative to other fields, the literature on network design using ML techniques is scarce, mainly focusing on multi-objective optimization problems (e.g., [155], [156], [157], [158]). Given the exploration space for the “optimal” network design, solving this multiobjective problem is strenuous. To ease this task, the work in [159] introduces knowledge from an expert to aid convergence to optimal solutions. Critical water infrastructure is often well-established, shifting the focus towards optimal sensor placement [160] and the design of DMA [161].

Maintaining the reliability of the water network is the top management priority. In essence, leak detection and fault prediction are the processes that assess the status of the WSS.

Some works, such as the one in [162], attempt to generally assess the status of the network. After guaranteeing the physical system’s reliability, the focus can shift to resource optimization, i.e., minimization of water and energy wastage.

C. EMULATING HYDRAULIC BEHAVIOURS

Traditionally, hydraulic simulation is achieved by using specific analytical formulations of the several components of the water network. Subsequent control strategies could take advantage of the analytical approach and transform the mathematical formulation (e.g., linearization) to implement specific control algorithms. While this approach can be straightforward for small networks, it becomes unfeasible when applied to more complex ones. Simulating larger WSS became more practical with the emergence of hydraulic simulators, such as EPANET [163]. However, building and calibrating virtual water networks is still a strenuous task, but the easy simulation of these systems is much more straightforward. ML models emerged as versatile tools to simulate hydraulic behavior. Water networks often have complex and nonlinear relationships between features, which ML techniques are able to handle. Technological advancements in computing hardware have narrowed any existing gap regarding computational efficiencies between EPANET and ML models. Despite this, the application of ML techniques to the field of water quality remains limited. Simulating water quality is more computationally intensive than hydraulic simulation due to the need for smaller time steps, longer simulation horizons, and the hydraulic behavior itself [164].

In order to train an ML model to be able to simulate the hydraulic behavior of a water network, a substantial amount of diverse data is necessary. Specifically, it is pertinent for the training data to considerably cover the distribution across all relevant feature spaces. Often, real-world datasets have a low number of data samples. Additionally, a WSS may have inadequate sensor infrastructure, which might lead to the creation of datasets that omit important features that capture hydraulic behavior. This can potentially explain why there are very few works when it comes to hydraulic state estimators that are trained with real-world data. A few examples of this are present in the works [165] and [166]. In the case of the work in [166], it was also categorized as having a mixed dataset due to using real water demands.

Due to the lack of real-world datasets, most ML models are trained on synthetic datasets, often generated by hydraulic simulators such as EPANET. Consequently, these models are classified as surrogate models. These surrogate models or metamodels (i.e., models of models) are well-explored in the domain of WSS and can be classified as response surface and lower-fidelity surrogates (see review [167]). The response surface models are data-driven and can often integrate uncertainty measurements, whereas lower-fidelity surrogates are physics-based but with much lower fidelity. Although lower-fidelity surrogates are a much less detailed version of

the original simulation, these can predict unexplored regions of features, making them suitable for extrapolation. There's a large body of literature on ML models used as surrogate models. According to the work in [168], these have been used for four main applications in WSS: optimization, real-time, uncertainty measurement, and state estimation. Although DL techniques are data-hungry, these are very good at learning the complex and nonlinear relations between features, hence why these are popularly used as hydraulic state estimators (e.g., [165], [166], [169], [170], [171], [172]). Other more traditional approaches, such as Gaussian-based methods, are still used (e.g., [173]).

As mentioned previously, the popularization of ML surrogate models is due to the scarcity of real-world datasets. Although the use of the synthetic datasets is useful, it is considered that the full potential of ML techniques remains unexplored, and some sub-fields are to be leveraged, such as Transfer Learning and Physics-Informed ML (see corresponding reviews in [174] and [175]).

The water network has its connections and junctions spread with a graph topology. Hydraulic behavior throughout the network is inherently connected to the pipe's interconnections. Specifically, an event at any node will affect adjacent nodes, which propagates until the event affects the entire network. This underscores the importance of the graph topology when using it as input for any ML model. Although frequently omitted, most works convert the network data into a tabular format for ingestion, which inherently loses valuable information to train ML techniques. There is an emergence of research works introducing graph representations to estimate hydraulic states [176] and applying GNN methodologies [177] and [178].

One notable issue of WSS datasets is the fact that frequently, some pertinent nodes of the network are not represented as a feature, i.e., some locations don't have sensor installed to acquire data. This makes learning the hydraulic behavior of the network much harder. However, some works exploit the topological format of the data to estimate hydraulic states in locations where no sensor information exists (e.g., [47]). These nodes in which data is estimated are referred to as virtual or soft sensors.

D. PREDICTIVE AND DECISION-MAKING CAPABILITIES FOR PUMP SCHEDULING

Optimal pump control for a WSS, both for pressure regulation and cost minimization, requires overcoming three main challenges. First of all, the collection and management of all necessary data in an actual control system is probably the most pertinent aspect. Secondly, being able to predict future states of the system is essential for optimal control algorithms. This is particularly true for Model Predictive Control (MPC), but Conventional Control algorithms (e.g., Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers) could also benefit from the knowledge of future states. Finally, the selection of the appropriate control algorithm is clearly

important. Regardless of the chosen control algorithm, the quality of its outputs is dependent on the quality of the predictive components, which subsequently is also dependent on the quality of the data used to develop corresponding predictive components. In general, in order for an MPC algorithm to output optimal pump schedules, it requires prediction of needed water demands and hydraulic behavior (given a control configuration).

Consumer water demands essentially dictate the quantity of water that must be pumped into the WSS. Unfortunately, unlike predicting future states of hydraulic systems, water demands aren't as deterministic since they are correlated to human activity. This implies that in order to maximize accuracy in forecasting water demands, the collection of real-world data is necessary. Most research works regarding water demand forecasting utilize weather conditions data to improve performance (e.g., [1], [179], [180], [181]). Other works exploit humans' inherent usage activity patterns as a collective. Specifically, some research works simply use historic water demands data (e.g., [182], [183], [184]), while others incorporate time-related attributes, such as the day of the week or seasonal variations (e.g., [185], [186], [187], [188]).

The literature on water demands forecasting presents a diverse range of methodologies. Traditional methods, such as ARIMA (e.g., [179], [188]) and RNN/LSTM (e.g., [185]), are commonly used. Additionally, other approaches have been explored, including Project Pursuit Regression [181], SVR/SVM (e.g., [182], [187], [189]), and novel methods, for instance, $\alpha\beta$ Water Demand Forecast [190] and Generalized Regression Neural Network [191], as implemented in [183].

Because a WSS might have a large number of water consumption nodes, monitoring each one with a sensor might be too costly. Either the topology of the water network is skeletonized, and sensors are applied in key locations or water consumers are profiled (e.g., [192], [193], [194]) in order to have a more fine-grained overview of the network. When individual customer water consumption data is available, it is possible to detect anomalies [189], which subsequently avoids physical attacks on the network (i.e., water theft).

As it is introduced clearly in the following sections, MPC algorithms require a surrogate model of the WSS. These algorithms generate multiple solutions, each one approximating to an optimal pump scheduling solution. Thus, there is a need for fast but accurate predictions. This can potentially explain why MPC algorithms often utilize equation representations (e.g., [195]), which can subsequently generate solutions with methods such as linear programming, nonlinear programming, and metaheuristics. An alternative to modeling directly the hydraulic behavior is learning indirectly through the objective function of the MPC algorithm. The works in [196] and [197] apply a Bayesian Optimization using a Gaussian Process (GP) and RF models as the "black-box" objective function.

As mentioned previously, ML techniques (particularly DL) can learn complex non-linear relationships, making them suitable for modeling hydraulic behavior. As an example,

the work in [198] utilizes an NN within an MPC algorithm. Although ML models have shown potential, they haven't gained traction specifically within MPC algorithms. This can be attributed to the fact that traditionally, ML models are trained from synthetically generated datasets from other representations, such as EPANET, which are calibrated with real-world data. This is because data acquired from sensors usually generate small and scarce datasets, and ML models might not be data-efficient enough to learn the relationships between these features effectively. Thus, in practice, if the ML model doesn't have the best inference speed, its implementation might not be justified. For ML models to be adopted in MPC algorithms, they must upgrade their capability to learn from real-world datasets.

Often, WSS can be so large that controlling them with a single algorithm becomes intractable. For proper management, partitioning the WSS into several subsections might be required. This approach can be problematic, as each portion can still affect other portions of the network. Consequently, control configurations that maximize certain objectives in a sub-network might negatively impact other portions of the WSS. The works in [199] and [200] address this by exploring the use of RL algorithms as "negotiators" between controllers of the several sub-networks. In essence, the RL algorithms attempt to induce cooperation behavior between the local agents by leveraging shared actuators (actuators used by more than one partition). Other control methods were found in the literature, such as RL (e.g., [201]), rule-based control ([202], [203]), or even using a decision tree to derive relationships between pump configurations given to the water network and resulting energy expenditure and water tank levels [204].

E. PRIVACY AND SECURITY

Although privacy and security are themes that shift away from the scope of this literature review, the considerable amount of research that is found deserves a brief examination. A large number of data samples is needed to train ML models effectively. For instance, the development of water demand forecasters requires the collection of water demands. Although this data can be collected at specific locations of the network, a more defined granularity (at the level of the household) might be needed in some cases. Accessing individual household's data might infringe on the privacy of the owners. Some works focus on the effective collection/usage of this data while maintaining a level of privacy. This could hypothetically be achieved by the implementation of designs involving blockchain [205] and federated learning [72].

Another aspect of maintaining the WSS well-functioning is ensuring integrity in the communication infrastructure. Specifically, errors might occur in the streaming of data from IoT sensors. Additionally, given the criticality of WSS, a fully automated management is inevitably susceptible to malicious attacks. There is some literature, in this context, that focuses on anomaly detection ([206], [207], [208], [209], [210]) and

the detection of potential intruders ([211], [212], [213]). Anomaly detection can also be used for physical intrusion, e.g., water theft [214]. ML techniques have a potential vulnerability in that they can be susceptible to adversarial attacks, where subtle intentional modifications to input data can cause the model to make incorrect predictions. The work in [127] investigates this issue by applying adversarial attacks for leakage detection.

VI. OPERATIONAL CONTROL IN WATER SUPPLY SYSTEMS

A. OVERVIEW OF STATE-OF-THE-ART ON CONTROL ALGORITHMS IN WSS

The collected research works focused on real-time operational management of WSS. The body of literature can be categorized as control algorithms focused on maintaining adequate pressure throughout the network or increasing the economic efficiency of the WSS, which can include cost reduction or even power generation. The former category also includes broad operational constraints, such as respecting proper water tank levels. As can be observed in Fig. 10, the number of works is somewhat balanced between the two categorical objectives. Research works focused on control algorithms in WSS have been slowly, but steadily, growing, with some spikes of publications on the category of System Reliability. It appears in recent years that the growth is slowing down. This could be a deprioritization of research work aimed at control for other fields (e.g., leak detection).

The control algorithms found in the literature were categorized as MPC, Conventional Control, RL, and Simplification Based. The Conventional Control category encompasses the "classic" control algorithms, such as PID and set-point-based controllers. The Simplification Based category refers specifically to works that leverage equation representations of the hydraulic system (e.g., steady-state equations) alongside the problem formulation and transform those mathematical representations to apply specific optimization algorithms. The linearization of the hydraulic behaviors is an example of a transformation applied to equation representations in the latter approach. Several observations can be made from Fig. 11. First of all, both MPC and Conventional Control methods were predominantly used throughout the years. Conventional Control algorithms take a significant role in pressure regulation due to their simplicity and real-time capabilities. In recent years, there has been a loss of interest in both of these methods. However, RL methods are starting to gain popularity. Nevertheless, the number of research works illustrated in Fig. 11 is small, and a confident conclusion cannot be taken.

Fig. 12 showcases the distribution of control algorithms over the mentioned operational objectives. Clearly, and as stated previously, Conventional Control algorithms are more often utilized for the purpose of pressure regulation. The MPC paradigm is particularly popular for minimizing costs due to its inherent capability to output controls based on

FIGURE 10. Distribution of Research Works by the objective of the operation.

FIGURE 11. Distribution of the type of control algorithms over time.

predicted future outcomes. Additionally, it facilitates explicit economic optimization because it allows for the formulation of the cost function directly in economic terms.

B. CONTROL FOR PRESSURE AND SYSTEM RELIABILITY

When managing a WSS, the top priority is ensuring its physical integrity. This includes respecting numerous

hydraulic constraints throughout the water network, such as maintaining adequate pressure in the several pipes and junctions, respecting water tank levels' limits, and being able to deliver the water to consumers, which can include the equitable distribution of water [215]. Failure to comply with WSS's hydraulic constraints results in the wastage of water and energy, as well as leading to damaged infrastructure.

FIGURE 12. Distribution of types of control algorithms over the economic focus and system reliability objectives.

For instance, high pressure in a junction can aggravate already existing leaks and create new ones. There are other considerations, such as avoiding frequent pump starts (i.e., on/off), which potentially reduces the actuator's lifetime.

Operational control for pressure regulation aims to deliver water to consumers at high enough pressures while avoiding damage to the infrastructure. Each water pump has a particular hydraulic curve representing the relationships between the flow of water, head, and energy expenditure. Pumps should be selected to work at optimal pressures, corresponding to the best efficiency point, in order to minimize energy and, consequently, cost. Some works, such as the ones in [216], [217], and [218], exploit this relationship to maximize pump efficiency. Although there are some research works focused solely on maintaining proper water tank levels [219], [220], the bulk of the literature aims at regulating the pressure throughout the network.

Managing pressure control throughout the water network can broadly be categorized into Local Pressure Control and Remote Pressure Control. The former entails setting pressure set-points downstream of the actuator, typically a Pressure Reducing Valve (PRV) (e.g., [221]). The latter category is based on the sensory upgrade in several key locations in the water network, allowing for the implementation of control algorithms that are aware of the hydraulic state of the system. Consequently, it allows for the implementation of a group of algorithms typically referred to in this category as Remote Real-Time Controllers (RRTC). The following works exploit this methodology: [222], [223], [224], [225], [226], [227], [228], [229], [230], and [231]. There are also works that utilize real-time operations to adapt to sudden faults (e.g., [232]). With the improvement of the sensory infrastructure, advanced iterations of this RRTC are emerging in the literature. For instance, the work in [233] exploits the high sam-

pling of data available and applies a frequency domain control design. These methodologies are usually borrowed for the design/rehabilitation of water networks, exploring how new changes to infrastructure affect the pressure distribution (e.g., [234]).

Because of the nature of the aforementioned approach to pressure regulation and its popularity, Conventional Control algorithms, such as PID controllers, are widely adopted in the literature (e.g., [235]). Some of the found Conventional Control algorithms integrate Multiple-Model Controllers (MMC), which assist in dealing with different hydraulic conditions (e.g., [171], and [218]). Simulators like EPANET, which use extended period steady-state simulation, are inadequate for capturing small and fast pressure changes and transient events such as leak occurrence. Most works that focus on pressure control through valve actuators opt to simulate hydraulic behavior through the use of unsteady flow models (e.g., [236], [237], [238], [239], [240]). This type of simulation is popular, and several research works have adopted software, such as WDNNextXL [241], that implements unsteady flow simulation [242].

Most of the presented pressure regulation/control algorithms are implemented from a holistic perspective over the water network but also in a decentralized manner. Specifically, very few works aim at applying global pump schedule systems that have a macro overview of all actuators and sensors, which makes sense given the prioritization of a quick reaction over sudden changes in pressure. Still, there are some works that focus on a global pressure regulation of the network (e.g., [243], [244], [245], [246], [247]). It was also found in the literature RL methodologies that focus on pressure control (e.g., [248], [249], [250]).

C. CONTROL FOR ECONOMIC GAINS

Clearly, avoiding damage to the infrastructure, mitigating leakages, and leveraging pump's efficiency curve to minimize energy expenditure all result in economic gains for the WSS. However, these aspects of WSS management predominantly revolve around the task of pressure regulation. This subsection focuses on research that formulates the pump control problem into directly minimizing costs or maximizing energy production. As seen previously, pressure regulation could often be done in a decentralized manner, considering that PRV could manage specific locations in the network susceptible to higher pressure events. However, effectively minimizing operational costs requires leveraging all the available information. Thus, the collection and subsequent utilization of knowledge seem to be more practical in a centralized manner. A notable exception to this is the work in [251], which utilizes bio-inspired information transfer. Some pressure regulation research works (e.g., [211], [252], [253], [254]) were also included in this category simply because they include parallel energy generation in the methodology.

In this context, the most dominant approach used in the literature was the MPC paradigm. This is not surprising considering that it aims to predict future states and leverage this knowledge to output adequate pump configurations. These controllers usually focus on solving the PSP. This problem formulation consists of scheduling the operation of pumps and/or valves to achieve certain goals (e.g., minimization of costs and respecting hydraulic constraints). For instance, an MPC would initially set up a certain pump schedule configuration and then predict how a system would react. Subsequently, predicted hydraulic states would be used to output a better pump schedule. Even though MPC are popular in the literature, a large portion of these systems focus on the mathematical formulation of the WSS's behavior, using an optimizer solver (which outputs the improved pump schedules) as an afterthought (e.g., [198], [255], [256], [257], [258], [259], [260], [261], [262]). Some examples of mentioned optimizers in the literature are IPOPT [263], COIN-OR [264], SCIP [265], Gurobi [266], CVX [267], and MOSEK [268].

In some cases, because both the hydraulic model and problem formulation are in an analytical format, these can be transformed (e.g., linearized) and optimization algorithms can be applied directly (e.g., [260], [269], [270], [271], [272]).

In the context of WSS's operational management, proper hydraulic simulations are the most important aspect of MPC methodologies. As was seen, a substantial amount of works in the literature utilize equation representations, which can be useful for proof of concepts but are not scalable to larger water networks. An alternative to this is the use of hydraulic simulators, such as EPANET (e.g., [273], [274], [275], [276], [277], [278], [279], [280], [281]), or using ML tools (e.g., [282], [283]). MPC methods are underutilized in real-world networks. It is surprising that ML tools are not yet explored in real-world settings, given their innate ability to learn any domain (with enough data). This might be an understatement of how hard it is to learn real-world hydraulic behaviors, whether it is due to the complexity of relationships or lack of large datasets. Additionally, it was found only one work that employed RL techniques to minimize costs [284], underscoring the complexity of this task.

VII. DISCUSSION: SYNERGY BETWEEN TECHNOLOGIES

A. REAL-TIME COMMUNICATION FRAMEWORK

As stated in earlier sections, one of the minimum requirements of a Digital Twin is its capability to have a continuous exchange of data between the physical entity and its digital counterpart. This feedback loop allows the continuous update of the digital representation and the real-world object's parameters or its associated control system. In essence, continuous communication permits real-time awareness and control over the physical entity.

Exploring the technical aspects of communication technologies (e.g., handling data transmission speeds, latency

management, and bandwidth requirements) is outside this work's scope, but it is important to understand why/how these affect the development of Digital Twins. First of all, the intended initial design of the Digital Twin was not monolithic but rather modular. Further proposed frameworks (e.g., [33]) reinforced this paradigm by modularizing each of the existing components (including the several services). Additionally, a data lake was also suggested to handle information coming from several sources. From a practical standpoint, in a real-world application, a modular design might be the most optimal choice because it allows the compartmentalization of each system's functionality.

As was observed previously, it is common for research to omit the aspect of communication. While the reasons for this are not known for certain, several hypotheses can be proposed. Firstly, the communication aspect can be neglected when presenting a proof of concept. This allows for the focus to be on the exploration of the potential gains of the Digital Twin technology. Secondly, developing a proper communication system requires advanced expertise and costs for deploying and running several modules.

Handling the information of each service is a complex task mainly because each implemented functionality can have different communication requirements. For instance, real-time communication is not only a requirement for practical pump control implementation but is also what is envisioned in the Digital Twin's conception. Furthermore, functionalities that exploit ML tools require huge amounts of data in order to achieve their maximum potential. It is then evident that the inclusion of ML tools in the Digital Twin requires large data storage units to be able to store huge volumes of data for training purposes and the capability to transfer those amounts of data. Although transferring large datasets between several services does not need to be done quickly, it might occur in parallel with other real-time communications. This, in turn, might strain the communication system. Besides the intra-communications within the Digital Twin, it is worth noting that the initial collection of data from the sensors might also incur some issues. If using distributed IoT networks, issues of data transmission and system efficiency might exist, addressed, for example, in [285].

Another aspect that adds complexity to the communication infrastructure is security. Digital Twins are often implemented in critical systems, as is the case for WSS. Many countermeasures should be implemented to avoid potential malicious actors, but there is always the risk of a potential flaw in the system. Consequently, this has delayed the implementation of these systems on the WSS. Nevertheless, some effort has been made in cyber-attack detection in order to ease concerns. This was evident in both the ML and Digital Twins literature reviews. In some of these works (e.g., [55] and [59]), the Digital Twin is often thought as a component inside of a CPS that supervises data streams. This framework design solves numerous problems. Firstly, having the CPS as a security layer checking for anomalies in data streams can

eventually ease restrictions in the autonomous management of WSS. Additionally, this solves previously mentioned problem of semantic idiosyncrasy in regard to the definitions of Digital Twins and CPS. Specifically, direct control of the real-world system will imply a hard coupling between the physical entity and the digital counterpart, i.e., making these two components dependent on each other. This is the definition of a CPS. On the other hand, there is somewhat of a consensus for the Digital Twin to have bidirectional continuous communications. This CPS and Digital Twin relationship might allow for these definitions to be true at the same time.

B. PREDICTIVE DIGITAL TWIN

A core tenet of the Digital Twin paradigm is having a Digital Model representative of the real-world system. Having a “mirror image” of the physical entity allows for upgraded monitoring and predictive capabilities. Consequently, the existence of a Digital Model leads to the implementation of more advanced tools, such as anomaly detection and MPC.

Particularly for the management of WSS, the advantages of having a Digital Model are multifaceted. A fundamental benefit is the enhancement of the monitoring system. Readily available access to metrics related to the system’s current state (e.g., through dashboards) significantly improves the decision-making of WSS operators.

The Digital Model does not restrict itself to emulating only hydraulic behaviors, but its usage expands to any aspect of managing a WSS, e.g., water demands, energy tariffs, and weather. In theory, a Digital Model is capable of predicting future states (encompassing all the aforementioned aspects). This, in turn, allows for an expansion of capabilities, such as what-if scenarios, MPC algorithms, anomaly detection, and predictive rehabilitation. All these abilities lead to an increase of efficiency and robustness in the management of a WSS.

In the overall literature, the emulation of hydraulic behaviors was mostly done for the purpose of control, usually in the MPC paradigm. A trend was observed where, generally, most of these research work applying control algorithms and hydraulic simulators/models were not used in real-world context.

EPANET was the most commonly used hydraulic simulator in the literature, which requires extensive calibration. Even with adequate calibration, it might still be unsuitable for real-world application if high accuracy is required. It was surprising to verify that ML tools were not as predominantly used for hydraulic simulation as one would have expected, due to their innate capability to learn any task domain when large quantity and good quality data exists. Their usage is mostly incentivized by their superior computational efficiency. It can be argued that the full potential of ML techniques as hydraulic simulators is being massively underused. Although most ML models were trained using synthetic data derived from EPANET, their transferability to real-world domains can still be achieved by leveraging domain adaptation techniques (e.g., transfer learning, domain

randomization, meta-learning). However, no research work has been found in the literature on these techniques for hydraulic behavior emulation.

Implementing predictive capabilities in Digital Twins, particularly in real-world applications, presents challenges such as the inevitable occurrence of concept drift. Concept drift refers to the change in the distribution of features over time, which can significantly impact the accuracy and reliability of predictive models (e.g., ML models). Some works were found in the literature aimed at solving this issue (e.g., [286]). In the WSS, concept drift can occur due to the slow degradation of the infrastructure, gradually changing hydraulic behaviors, or due to sudden changes, such as a fault in a component. Consequently, hydraulic simulators, which were calibrated/trained on previous states of the system will then require an update. In the context of continuous application of ML tools, the slow-changing domain will hinder its effectiveness. Closely monitoring the ML model and frequently retraining it with new information can mitigate this issue. However, this approach introduces the risk of “Catastrophic Forgetting”, where an ML model, if continuously trained with new data, may eventually ‘forget’ previously learned valuable information. The work by [287] tries to ease this issue by choosing the most pertinent data samples to update the ML model.

C. SMART PREDICTIVE DIGITAL TWIN

Effective management of the WSS encompasses multiple dimensions, ranging from the real-time knowledge of the infrastructure’s states, leading to the detection/prediction/resolution of faults, to the optimal operation of the existent actuators in the system. To achieve optimal decision-making, one needs to leverage all the existing knowledge of the current state of the water network alongside data generated by predictor and analytical tools. Only with enough data can any DSS provide adequate decision-making capabilities, i.e., the “smart” capability.

Installing sensors throughout the WSS, alongside the communication infrastructure, is costly, but the need for more network knowledge is becoming increasingly evident. Additionally, developing systems that focus on the collection from numerous data sources, and leveraging ML and DSS algorithms can improve utilization of the water-energy nexus, as noted in [288].

With a proper monitoring framework set up, in practice, the real-time data streams should automatically be transmitted to a data lake for the collection of historical data or directly into analytical tools for the detection of any issue or simply for monitoring the “health” of the infrastructure. Specifically, continuously transmitted data can be used to detect/predict problems that might occur in the water network. Examples of some potential applications were found in the ML literature review: leak detection and location, fault prediction, and anomaly detection. A quick detection of any disruptive event in the water network will allow for an equally fast response and adaptation of existing control algorithms. For instance,

TABLE 6. ML Research works implemented in WSS for hydraulic estate estimation/calibration purposes.

Citations	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of ML	Hydraulic Modeling	Network Case-study	Type of Datasets
[196]	Journal	2018	RF, GP	EPANET	Anytown, Milan (Italy)	Mixed
[195]	Journal	2018	Multivariate linear regression curve-fitting method	EPANET	BWSN, Richmond	Synthetic
[47]	Journal	2022	Temporal Graph CNN	EPANET, WNTR	Patio-villa del Rosario (Colombia) C-Town network	Synthetic
[171]	Journal	2020	NN, RNN, LSTM, Decision Tree, RF	Equations	Laboratory	Real
[198]	Conference	2020	NN	EPANET	C-Town	synthetic
[176]	Journal	2022	Graph signal processing	EPANET	2 Unnamed networks	Synthetic
[165]	Journal	2022	Statistical models: ETS, ARIMA ML models: SVR, RF, XGBoost, CNN, LSTM	undefined	Singapore	Real
[173]	Conference	2019	GP regression	EPANET	Hanoi	Synthetic
[197]	Conference	2020	GP, RF	EPANET	Milan (Italy)	Mixed
[169]	Conference	2020	NN, Decision Tree, Rf	Equations	Laboratory	Mixed
[172]	Journal	2022	NN	EPANET	Mays network	Synthetic
[287]	Journal	2022	PCA	undefined	Awnet (from Anglian Water)	Real
[177]	Journal	2023	GNN	WNTR	Apulian network	Synthetic
[170]	Journal	2022	NN	EPANET	Network from [78]	Synthetic
[166]	Journal	2023	NN	EPANET	Fossolo	Mixed
[178]	Journal	2023	GNN, NN	EPANET	Fossolo, BakRyan, Pescara Modena, Marchi Rural, KL	Synthetic

TABLE 7. ML research works which do not fall in defined categories.

Citations	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of ML	Input Features
[289]	Journal	2022	NN	General
[199]	Conference	2010	RL	System State
[162]	Journal	2012	Decision Tree	Pressure; Height; Pipe Length; Elevation; Pipe Roughness
[200]	Conference	2019	RL	Water demand; flow; Water Tank Levels; Valve Positions; Pump Status; Topology; Weather Conditions; Temperature
[72]	Conference	2022	Federated Averaging (FedAvg)	General

TABLE 8. ML Research works implemented in WSS for WSS's network design purposes.

Citation	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of ML	Input Features
[156], [155], [157]	Conference	2005	Learnable Evolution Model	Network Designs
[161]	Journal	2019	K-means; Self-organizing map	Water Demand, Node Elevation, Pipe length
[160]	Conference	2021	KNN	Pressure
[158]	Journal	2021	Selection hyper-heuristic approach	Historical Heuristic Selections; Performance metrics
[159]	Conference	2020	RF	Pipe Attributes, Pressure, Flow

TABLE 9. ML Research works implemented in WSS for Direct Control purposes.

Citation	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of ML	Input Features
[201]	Journal	2021	RL	Pressure
[203]	Conference	2023	Logic Learning Machine	Historical Hydraulic data (including pump status)
[202]	Journal	2023	Logic Learning Machine	Pump Status, Pressure, Water Demands, Water Tank Levels, Energy Consumption

the occurrence of a pipe burst is an event that affects the hydraulic behavior throughout the water network in a cascading manner. Hence, applied control algorithms need to be alerted to the changing of hydraulic properties to manage the WSS still effectively. Furthermore, all the data being transmitted either from the physical entity, the Digital Model, or any other existing services can be stored in data lakes and subsequently be repurposed, for instance, to train/validate ML models.

A complete operational management of WSS can be viewed in a hierarchical manner. First of all, pressure regulation is probably the most important aspect when it comes to maintaining system pressure and reliability. Sudden pressure changes might occur in the system, and

if not handled as quickly, they might incur damage to the infrastructure. Additionally, these sporadic events occur in specific locations in the network, so full global knowledge of the network is not required in this modality of control. Conventional Control algorithms (usually controlling a PRV) are often used in this context due to their innate capability to offer adequate control settings in real-time. Some works focus on designing DMA and using these control methods (e.g., [41]) to validate whether pressure regulation can be properly handled.

The secondary priority in managing the WSS is focused on economic efficiency. Unlike previously, a centralized unit/service needs to exist to collect all available data in order to produce an informed decision. As it was mentioned, this data can either be from sensors or from outputs from other predictor tools within the Digital Twin. The MPC paradigm is very commonly applied here. MPC controllers are dependent on the model used to simulate the system. The literature verified a lack of ML models being used, even with all their potential, with EPANET being predominantly used. Scalability might be an issue when applying the MPC paradigm. Not only does proper data management need to

TABLE 10. ML Research works implemented in WSS for water demands purposes.

Citation	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of ML	Network Case-study	Type of training datasets
[181]	Journal	2010	NN, Projection Pursuit Regression, Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines, RF, SVR	Unnamed Network (Spain)	Real
[189]	Journal	2017	Proposed Time-series clustering, SVR	Milan (Italy)	Real
[182]	Journal	2019	SVM with radial basis function	Milan (Italy)	Real
[188]	Conferences	2014	ARIMA, SVM	Germany	Real
[183]	Journal	2019	$\alpha \beta$ Water Demand Forecast [190], Generalized Regression Neural Network [191]	Unnamed Network (Spain)	Real
[185]	Journal	2021	NN, LSTM, SRNN, GRU	Unnamed Network, Trentino (Italy)	Mixed
[186]	Journal	2019	KNN	Unnamed network (Spain)	Real
[194]	Conference	2017	K-means, Fourier Regression Mixture Model	From Syndicat des Eaux d'Il-de-France (France)	Real
[179]	Conference	2022	ARIMA, NN, SVR, LightGBM, LSTM, Wavelet Data-Driven Forecasting framework	Milan (Italy)	Real
[180]	Journal	2023	Gradient boosted regression tree	Unnamed Network (China)	Real
[184]	Journal	2023	Facebook Prophet Project	Stembert water station	Real
[187]	Conference	2019	Linear Regression, SVR, NN	Unnamed Network	Real

TABLE 11. Digital Twins implementations on WSS.

Citations	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Communication Type	Data Storage	Digital Model	Services	Case-study
[35]	Journal	2020	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data, including Water Demands; Virtual-to-Physical: Hydraulic Data, Potential for Control	SCADA	GO2HydNet (EPANET-based)	Network Design, Leak Detection, Operational optimization, Water Quality, Emergency Response	Real Valencia (Spain)
[53]	Journal	2022	Physical-to-Virtual: Water Demands; Virtual-to-Physical: Unspecified	SCADA	EPANET	Impact Assessment	Real Historical Data from Lakewood (USA)
[51]	Journal	2022	Physical-to-Virtual: General Hydraulic Data (Flow, pressure, water demands); Virtual-to-Physical: Controls	Implied SCADA	Equations	Leakage Detection, Pressure Control	Real Historical data from Lisboa (Portugal)
[55]	Conference	2021	Physical-to-Virtual: General Hydraulic Data; Virtual-to-Physical: Anomaly Detection	Unspecified	Timed Automaton Machine, Utilizes a GAN (GCN-LSTM) architecture for anomaly detection	Anomaly Detection	Synthetic SWaT, WADI, BATADAL
[43]	Journal	2020	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data; Virtual-to-Physical: Hydraulic data	Hadoop-based distributed data center	EPANET	Dynamic Demand Assignment	Real Historical Data from Unnamed Network (USA)
[47]	Journal	2022	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data (Pressure and Flows); Virtual-to-Physical: Pump Speeds	Unspecified	EPANET, T-GNN	Hydraulic State Estimation	Synthetic Patios Network-Villa del Rosario, C-Town
[36]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data (Pressure and flow); Virtual-to-Physical: Anomaly Detection	Unspecified	Unspecified ML	Anomaly Detection	Real Historical Data from Singapore
[56]	Conference	2020	Physical-to-Virtual: Pump Status; Virtual-to-Physical: Control	SQLite	WNTR	Anomaly Detection	Synthetic C-Town
[42]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data (Pressure and Flows); Virtual-to-Physical: PRV control; Network configuration	Implied SCADA	EPANET	Water Loss Reduction, Network Design	Synthetic with Real historical data from Madeira (Portugal)
[41], [40], [39], [38], [37]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Topological data, Hydraulic Data; Virtual-to-Physical: Analysis output	Unspecified	WDNextXL- -WDNetGIS	Topological Analysis, Hydraulic Model Calibration, Network Design, Pressure control, System Rehabilitation	Synthetic Modugno, Bari (Italy)
[57]	Conference	2020	Physical-to-Virtual: Water Levels; Virtual-to-Physical: Anomaly Detection	Unspecified	Equations	Anomaly Detection	Laboratory
[54]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data (pressure, flow); Virtual-to-Physical: Control Configuration	Unspecified	Equations	Hydropower Generation; Pressure Control	Synthetic Sicily (Italy)
[48]	Conference	2022	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data (Flow and Pressure); Virtual-to-Physical: Hydraulic Behavior	Unspecified	LSTM	Fault Prediction	Real Historical data from [80]
[49]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data; Virtual-to-Physical: Leak Detection	Unspecified	Generative Model (Wasserstein Autoencoder)	Leak Localization	Synthetic Hanoi, NET3, Modena
[50]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Topology; Virtual-to-Physical: Potentially Hydraulic Simulation	Unspecified	WATERing (EPANET-based)	Construction of an Hydraulic Model	Real Historical Data from Pamplona (Colombia)
[44]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data; Virtual-to-Physical: Control	Blockchain	Vague	Data Standardization	Real Historical Data
[58]	Conference	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data, including Control Configuration; Virtual-to-Physical: Anomaly Detection	Unspecified	Hybrid Automaton	Anomaly Detection	Synthetic WADI
[34]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data; Virtual-to-Physical: Control configuration	ThingSpeak (cloud-based)	EPANET	Leak Detection	Laboratory
[52]	Journal	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data (Pressure and Flow); Water Quality; Virtual-to-Physical: Leak Detection, Disinfectant Doses	Unspecified	EPANET	Water Quality regulation, Leak Detection	Synthetic C-Town
[60]	Conference	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data, General System Status; Virtual-to-Physical: Runtime Verification Outcomes	Unspecified	Unspecified	Anomaly Detection	Synthetic C-Town
[59]	Conference	2023	Physical-to-Virtual: Hydraulic Data, Control Configuration; Virtual-to-Physical: Anomaly Detection	Vague	Hybrid Automaton	Anomaly Detection	Synthetic WADI

be considered, but a larger WSS might also increase the computational processing time of hydraulic simulators and

optimization algorithms. An idea to handle this scalability problem might be to subdivide the water network into several

TABLE 12. ML Research works implemented in WSS for leak detection purposes.

Citation	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of ML model	Input Features	Network/Case-study	Type of Datasets
[88]	Journal	2019	Empirical Mode Decomposition, PCA, SVM,	Wireless Data Collected	Unnamed Network	Real
[93]	Journal	2022	Decision Tree, KNN, RF, Adaboost	Index Efficiency, Std. of Acceleration	Hong kong (China)	Real
[84]	Journal	2021	Decision Tree, KNN, RF, Bayesian Network	Flow	Leeuwarden (Netherlands)	Real
[95]	Conference	2014	Network-based spectral clustering, SVM	Pressure, Flow	Milan (Italy), Timisoara (Romania)	Synthetic
[90]	Journal	2022	Decision Tree, SVM, KNN, NN	Acoustic Signals	Hong kong (China)	Real
[96]	Journal	2020	K-means Clustering, RF	Pressure, Flow	Benchmark from [79]	Synthetic
[89]	Journal	2021	KNN	Pressure	Tnet1	Synthetic
[97]	Journal	2018	Bayesian Probabilistic, SVM, NN	Pressure, Flow	2 Unnamed networks Laboratory	Mixed
[98]	Journal	2022	Resnet	Pressure	Anytown, NET3	Synthetic
[99]	Conference	2017	K-means, RBF, GP, RF, SVM	Pressure, Flow	Timisoara (Romania)	Synthetic
[87]	Journal	2022	Frequency Convolutional NN, Time-Frequency Convolutional NN	Acoustic Signals	Sydney (Australia)	Real
[86]	Journal	2023	Decision Tree, Giant Boosted Trees, RF, NN, Naive Bayes Kernel, SVM, Rule Induction, Linear Regression	Acoustic signals	Hong Kong (China)	Real
[100]	Conference	2020	KNN, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Linear Discriminator	Pressure	Hanoi	Synthetic
[85]	Conference	2021	Gaussian Mixture Model, bayesian Gaussian Mixture Model, Isolation Forest, RealNVP, Deep Convolutional Autoencoder, Adversarial autoencoder, Adversarial Variational Bayes	Acoustic Signals	Germany	Mixed
[123]	Journal	2022	NN	Flow, Pressure, Water Consumption	Hanoi	Synthetic
[101]	Journal	2022	XGBoost	Water Usage Period, Pipe Depth, Flow, Pressure	Ningxia (China)	Real
[102]	Journal	2023	NN, SVM	Pressure, Flow	Hanoi	Synthetic
[103]	Journal	2023	Elastic-net Logistic Regression Model	Pressure	Bk-Town	Mixed
[104]	Journal	2023	LSTM Autoencoders	Flow, Pressure	Hanoi	Mixed (Real water demands)
[105]	Journal	2023	Canonical Discriminant Function, k-means, Learning Vector Quantization (and variants), Dunn Index, Davies-Bouldin Index	Pressure	Stockholm (Sweden)	Real
[106]	Conference	2020	CNN	Pressure	Cherry hill/Brushy plains, New York Tunnel, Fossolo	Synthetic
[107]	Conference	2021	Logistic Regression, SVM	Pressure, Flow, Temperature, Pump Frequency	Pilani (India)	Real
[112]	Conference	2018	SVM	Pressure, Flow	Pilani, India	Synthetic
[91]	Journal	2022	Frequency Convolutional NN Time-Frequency Convolutional NN	Vibro-acoustic Data	Sydney (Australia)	Real
[110]	Journal	2023	Linear regression Multinomial Logistic Regression	Pressure, Flow	Hanoi, NET3, C-Town	Synthetic
[111]	Conference	2020	SVM, KNN, RF	Pressure	Hanoi, Fossolo, Modena	Synthetic
[122]	Journal	2023	Proposed method with Maximum Mean Difference Metric, K-means, KNN, SVM, NN, RF	Pressure	Unnamed Network	Mixed
[109]	Conference	2023	Isolation Forest, SVM, RNN-LSTM	Pressure, Flow	Dubai (Unites Arab Emirates)	Real
[108]	Conference	2022	Bidirectional LSTM	Water Consumption, Flow	Unnamed Network (Philippines)	Real
[114]	Conference	2022	SVM	Pressure	Laboratory	Real
[115]	Conference	2022	K Neighbor Classifier, Decision Tree, RF, Adaboost Classifier, SVM, Radial Basis function, Gaussian Naive Bayes	Water Demand, Pressure	Networks a,b,c (constructed in LoRaSURFING)	Synthetic
[113]	Journal	2023	1-d CNN	Pressure, Flow, Temperature	Laboratory	Real
[124]	Conference	2023	Bidirectional LSTM	Water Consumption	Unnamed Network (United Kingdom (UK))	Real
[94]	Conference	2023	NN, SVM, Decision Tree	Accelerometer Data	Laboratory	Real
[121]	Conference	2022	Gaussian Naive Bayes Classifier	Pressure	BK-Town	Mixed
[92]	Conference	2023	XGBoost, Gradient Boosting, RF	Vibration	Unnamed Network	Real
[125]	Conference	2022	C-means clustering, NN	Pressure	Xuancheng (China)	Synthetic
[126]	Conference	2023	SVM, NN	Pressure, Flow	Surat (India)	Synthetic
[116]	Journal	2023	Autoencoder, 3D-CNN, RF, ConvLSTM	Pressure, Flow	D-Town	Synthetic
[127]	Conference	2023	Linear Regression	Pressure	Hanoi, L-Town	Synthetic
[117]	Journal	2023	KNN, Linear Discriminant Classifiers	Pressure	Hanoi, DMA in Madrid	Mixed
[128]	Journal	2020	RF	Pressure, Flow	Casablanca (Morocco)	Mixed
[118]	Journal	2023	Autoencoder, LSTM, Gated Recurrent Unit Temporal-Graph CNN	Pressure	BK-Town (Belgium)	Mixed
[119]	Journal	2023	Elastic-net logistic regression model Autoencoders	Pressure, Flow, GIS, CRM	BK-Town	Mixed
[120]	Conference	2023	SVM, NN	Flow, Pressure, Temperature	Unnamed Network	Synthetic

sections and apply MPC controllers on each. Clearly, these will still have an effect on each other, so managing the several entities is crucial. Some works, such as the one in [200], applied RL to manage the interaction between agents.

The implementation of Digital Twins for the management of complex systems (e.g., WSS) naturally converges to the emergence of Smart Predictive Digital Twins. This concept is discussed indirectly throughout this work with the review of its related technologies, applied to WSS, namely: Digital Twins, ML models, and DSS/control algorithms. By exploring these technologies in isolation and their interactions, this review captures the potential and limitations of Smart Predictive Digital Twins. In this work, the Smart Predictive Digital Twin is defined as a Digital

Twin that integrates decision-making algorithms explicitly leveraging predictive models. Although control algorithms can solely use real-time data, their behavior is fundamentally reactive. In contrast, the integration of predicted data allows the decision-making algorithms to enable anticipatory behavior. Thus, the integration of predictive capabilities in decision-making is considered a necessary attribute of Smart Predictive Digital Twins.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This literature review was designed to assess future trends of Digital Twins and related technologies as well as current synergies. The broad approach in the selection of research works allowed for a comprehensive macro perspective on the

TABLE 13. ML Research works implemented in WSS for fault prediction purposes.

Citation	Publication Type	Year of Publication	ML model	Input Features	Network Case-study
[143]	Journal	2018	Boosted Decision Trees	Historical Data, Pipe Attributes, Other External Factors, Other Network Characteristics	Austria
[147]	Journal	2019	Extreme learning machine (ELM)	Historical Data, Pipe Attributes	Canada
[133]	Journal	2020	Gradient-Boosted tree, Bayes SVM, NN, Linear Regression, Poisson Regression, Evolutionary polynomial regressions	Historical Data, Pipe Attributes, Terrain Quality, Other Network Characteristics, Other External Factors	Colombia
[151]	Journal	2019	SVM, PCA, GP Regression, NN	Pipe Attributes	Iran
[130]	Journal	2020	Regression models: TLM, TEM, Poisson GLM, Naive Bayes, Zero-inflated Poisson GLM, Zero-inflated NB GLM, SVM, Probabilistic Models: Logistic GLM, LDA, Boosting Gradient, RF, NN	Historical Data, Pipe Attributes, Weather, Terrain Quality, Other Network Characteristics	UK
[145]	Journal	2021	Logistic Regression	Terrain Quality, Historical Data, Pipe Attributes, Other Network Characteristics	UK
[138]	Journal	2023	LSTM, ARIMAX	Weather Factors, Historical Data	USA
[139]	Journal	2021	RF, Boosted Regression Tree, Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines, NN	Historical Data, Pipe Attributes, Weather, Other Network Characteristics	USA
[132]	Journal	2020	NN	Pipe Attribute, Terrain Quality, Historical Data, Other External Factors	Unnamed
[150]	Journal	2022	NN, Multiple Linear Regression	Pipe Attributes, Other Network Characteristics	Egypt
[134]	Journal	2023	Discriminant Analysis, RF, Logistic Regression	Pipe Attributes, Other Network Characteristics, Historical Data, Terrain Quality, Other External Factors	Spain
[140]	Journal	2022	RF, Logistic Regression	Historical Data, Pipe Attributes, Other External Factors	China
[152]	Journal	2021	NN	Pipe Attributes, Historical Data, Other Network Characteristics	Spain
[131]	Journal	2022	RF	Pipe Attributes, Historical Data, Other External Factors	Norway
[141]	Journal	2021	Elman Neural Network, NN	Pipe Attributes, Other External Factors	Shattora, Egypt
[135]	Conference	2020	Logistic Regression, SVM, Classification Tree, RF	Pipe Attributes, Historical Data, Terrain Quality, Other Network Characteristics, Other External Factors	USA
[146]	Conference	2020	General Regression NN, Linear Regression, NN, SVM	Pipe Attributes	Egypt
[142]	Journal	2020	Decision Tree	Historical Data, Other External Factors	China
[136]	Conference	2017	Infinite Gamma-Poisson Mixture Model, Hierarchical	Pipe Attributes, Terrain Quality, Historical Data	Unnamed
[149]	Journal	2019	Hierarchical Dirichlet process mixture of hierarchical beta process	Historical Data	Unnamed
[137]	Conference	2020	Gradient boosting techniques	Pipe Attributes, Historical Data, Terrain Quality, Other Network Characteristics	Australia
[73]	Journal	2023	Logistic Regression, RF, Gradient Boosting Decision Tree	Pipe Attribute, Historical Data, Terrain Quality, Other External Factors	USA
[153]	Journal	2023	Adaptive Regression Splines, CNN, SVM	Pipe Attributes, Other Network Characteristics	Iran
[129]	Conference	2022	Gradient Boosting Trees, LighGBM, XGBoost	Other Network Characteristics	Hanoi, Net3, Anytown
[144]	Journal	2023	RF	Other Network Characteristics	NetA, NetB
[148]	Journal	2021	Hierarchical Dirichlet Process Mixture Model, Hierarchical Beta Process	Historical Data	Unnamed
[154]	Conference	2021	NN	Pipe Attributes, Historical Data, Network Characteristics	Romania

TABLE 14. ML Research works implemented in WSS for data management purposes purposes.

Citation	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of ML	Input Features
[192]	Conference	2021	K-means, Decision Tree, RF, NN, RNN	Water Consumption
[205]	Conference	2020	K-means++	Consumer Data (Implied)
[193]	Conference	2021	K-means, Decision Tree, RF, NN, RNN	Water Consumption, Postal Code, Customer Class
[204]	Conference	2021	Decision Tree	Pump Operation Controls
[286]	Conference	2023	Autoencoder	Data Streams (Vague on data details)
[285]	Journal	2021	NN	Data Samples from IoT devices

TABLE 15. ML Research works implemented in WSS for Anomaly and CyberAttack Detection purposes.

Citation	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of ML	Network/Case-study	Type of training datasets
[206]	Journal	2021	Gaussian Distribution, K-means, Isolation Forest, SVM, Autoencoders	Unnamed Network	Real
[211]	Conference	2017	RF	C-town	Synthetic
[208]	Journal	2016	SVR, K-means, Gaussian Mixture Model	From Vitens Innovation Playground (Netherlands)	Real
[209]	Journal	2019	Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN)	Vitens	Real
[210]	Journal	2020	Variational Bayesian Inference	Unnamed Network (Ethiopia)	Real
[214]	Journal	2023	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN), Lempel-ziv complexity	Unnamed Network (Iran)	Real
[213]	Conference	2022	Naive Bayes, PCA, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, KNN, SVM	SWaT	Synthetic

chosen themes, and thus, it also enhanced the capability to understand the current state of affairs and predict the future directions of these technologies.

In this work, the three initially stated research questions are answered, which defined the thematic objective of the literature review.

- **RQ1 - In the literature, is there any system built that could be considered a full implementation of a Smart Predictive Digital Twin?** In this work, requirements for a system to be considered a Digital Twin were defined. Specifically, it needs to have a Digital Model, and it needs to communicate with the Physical Twin

TABLE 16. Real-time Control and Decision Support System algorithms with the control objective of system reliability.

Citation	Publication Type	Year of Publication	Type of Control/DSS Algorithm	Optimization Objective	Predictive Components	Actuator	Validation Environment
[222]	Journal	2010	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Networks [78] and [77]
[221]	Journal	2013	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Unnamed network (Italy)
[228]	Journal	2018	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Real Benevento (Italy)
[231]	Journal	2018	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Laboratory
[227]	Journal	2016	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Municipality of Oppegård (Norway)
[236]	Journal	2017	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Unnamed network (Italy)
[51]	Journal	2022	NLP	Pressure Control	Equations	Valve	Synthetic Equations; Real Historical data Lisbon (Portugal)
[237]	Journal	2020	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Castelfranco Emilia (Italy)
[238]	Journal	2019	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Unnamed network, Castelfranco Emilia (Italy)
[223]	Conference	2015	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Municipality of Oppegård (Norway)
[232]	Journal	2018	NSGA-II	Pressure Control Short-time Response to an unplanned failure	No	Valve	Synthetic C-Town
[226]	Journal	2017	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	Polynomial Regression	Valve	Synthetic Castelfranco Emilia (Italy)
[216]	Journal	2020	RL	Pump Efficiency	No	Pump	Synthetic Anytown, C-Town, D-Town
[242]	Journal	2017	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Apulian network [242], Municipality of Oppegård (Norway)
[220]	Journal	2009	Conventional Control	Water Levels	No	Pump	Synthetic Bangalore and Faridabad (India), Gaziantep (Turkey) [76]
[171]	Journal	2020	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Pump	Real Laboratory
[241]	Conference	2015	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Apulian network
[225]	Journal	2018	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Castelfranco Emilia (Italy)
[224]	Journal	2018	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Municipality of Oppegård (Norway)
[233]	Journal	2020	Conventional Control	Pressure Control Cost of Control	No	Valves	Synthetic Unnamed Network, Castelfranco Emilia (Italy)
[230]	Conference	2017	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Real Laboratory
[229]	Journal	2020	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Real Laboratory
[244]	Journal	2020	Interior Point Convex algorithm	Pressure control	Linear Models	Pump Station	Synthetic Shanghai (China) with Real Historical Data
[234]	Journal	2020	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic San Giovanni la Punta (Italy)
[250]	Conference	2021	RL	General	No	Pump	Synthetic Network, [75]; Real Smart Water Infrastructure Laboratory, [74]
[217]	Conference	2017	Conventional Control	Pressure Control, Pump Efficiency	No	Pump	Synthetic Unnamed network
[245]	Journal	2023	MPC (solved with MOSEK)	Pressure Control	LVP	Valve	Synthetic Castelfranco Emilia (Italy)
[215]	Conference	2017	Conventional Control; MPC	General	Equations	Valve	Synthetic Bangalore (India) with Real Historical data
[219]	Journal	2019	Conventional Control	Regulation of Water Tanks Levels	No	Pump	Synthetic Sidi Aich (Algeria)
[236]	Conference	2017	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Castelfranco Emilia (Italy)
[248]	Conference	2021	RL	General	No	Pump Station	Synthetic Bjerlingbro (Denmark)
[246]	Conference	2018	MPC, Conventional Control	Pressure Control	EPANET	Valve	Synthetic Unnamed (Canada)
[235]	Conference	2014	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Pump	Unclear
[240]	Journal	2023	Conventional Control (Internal ModelControl)	Pressure Control	LVP	Valve	Synthetic Castelfranco Emilia (Italy)
[243]	Conference	2023	SCP (solved with CVX)	Pressure Control	Equations	Pump	Synthetic Thai Nguyen (Vietnam)
[218]	Conference	2020	Conventional Control	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Real Laboratory
[249]	Conference	2022	RL	Pressure Control	No	Valve	Synthetic Barcelona (Spain)

continuously in real-time. However, for this system to be a Smart Predictive Digital Twin, it also must incorporate decision-making capabilities leveraging predictive analytics. The intersection between all these characteristics was nonexistent in this academic literature review. Only the work in [34] applied real-world, real-time communications and implemented analytical tools to detect and locate leaks, but it did not have a predictive component directly used by the controllers. However, in the commercial literature review, some Digital Twins presented the capability of operating actuators of the WSS while leveraging predictive components. Consequently, these Digital Twins can be considered Smart Predictive Digital Twins.

Some additional nuance regarding the academic vs. commercial Digital Twins needs to be clarified.

Although the commercial review presents cutting-edge technologies, such as the Smart Predictive Digital Twins, these sources inherently have some bias when publicizing their products/services' functionalities. Additionally, the closed-source nature makes learning the implemented methodologies untractable. In contrast, academic research is, by definition, transparent and trustworthy due to peer review and open methodologies. Therefore, while Smart Predictive Digital Twins were identified in the commercial review, it is essential to approach these purported technologies with caution.

- **RQ2 - What are the emerging trends (area of application or technology) in implementing Smart Predictive Digital Twins?** In the ML literature review, the field of application "Leak Detection and

TABLE 17. Real-time Control and Decision Support System algorithms with the control objective of cost reduction.

Citations	Publication Type	Year	Type of Control/DSS Algorithm	Optimization Objective	Predictive Components	Actuator	Validation Environment
[269]	Journal	2012	Linear Programming Greedy local search	Minimization of Costs	Equations, EPANET	Pump	Synthetic Anytown, Richmond
[282]	Journal	2007	GA	Minimize Costs	NN	Pump	Synthetic Anytown
[283]	Journal	2007	GA	Minimization of Costs	NN	Pump, Valve	Synthetic Haifa-A
[255]	Journal	2014	MPC (solved with fmincon from matlab)	Minimization of costs	Equations	Pump, Valve	Synthetic Unnamed Network
[273]	Journal	2015	Multialgorithm Genetically-Adaptive-Method (AMALGAM)	Minimization of Costs, System Reliability	EPANET, Dynamic Neural Network (DAN2-H)	Pump	Synthetic Araraquara (Brazil)
[270]	Journal	2009	MILP	Minimization of costs, Maximization of Pump efficiency	Equations	Pump, Valve	Real California, Johnson County, Maryland (USA)
[252]	Journal	2016	Conventional Control	Maximization of Energy Production, Pressure Control	No	Valve	Laboratory
[256]	Journal	2018	MPC (solved with Proximal Gradient Algorithm)	Minimization of costs	Equations	Pump, Valve	Synthetic Barcelona (Spain) with Real Historical Data
[279]	Journal	2018	PSO, Nonlinear AutoRegressive with eXogenous input NN (NARX), Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF)	Minimization of cost	EPANET	Pump, Valve	Synthetic D-Town; Real Historical data from Franca (Brazil)
[257]	Conference	2014	MPC (solved with CPLEX)	Minimization of costs	Equations	Pump	Synthetic Barcelona (Spain)
[280]	Conference	2014	GA	Minimization of Costs	EPANET	Pump	Real Unnamed Network
[271]	Journal	2020	MILP	Minimization of Costs	Equations	Pump	Synthetic Sopron (Hungary) with Real Historical data
[281]	Journal	2015	GA	Minimization of Costs	EPANET	Pump	Real Seoul (South Korea)
[261]	Journal	2020	Chance-Constrained Optimization (solved with Gurobi)	Minimization of Costs	Equations	Pump Valve	Synthetic Unnamed Network
[251]	Conference	2010	Decentralized Self-Organizing Multi-Agent System Coordinated by Indirect Defense Coordination Mechanism	Minimization of Costs	Linear Regression	Pump	Synthetic Unnamed Network
[274]	Journal	2018	Mixed-integer Differential evolution	Minimization of Costs	Equation	Pump	Synthetic Unnamed (United Kingdom)
[275]	Journal	2021	MPC with MINP	Minimization of Costs	Equations	Pump	Synthetic Richmond
[259]	Journal	2015	MPC with Quadratic programming	Minimization of costs, General System Reliability	Equations	Pump	Synthetic Barcelona (Spain) with Real Historical Data
[198]	Conference	2020	MPC (non-explicit solver)	Minimization of costs	NN	Pump, Valve	Synthetic C-Town
[253]	Journal	2020	Conventional Control	Pressure Control, Maximization of Energy Production	No	Pump	Laboratory
[258]	Conference	2019	Chance-Constrained Optimization solved with IPOPT	Minimization of costs	Equations	Pump, Valve	Synthetic Unnamed Network
[284]	Journal	2023	RL	Minimization of costs	No	Pump	Synthetic NET3
[276]	Conference	2017	GA	Minimization of Costs	EPANET	Pump	Synthetic Unnamed Network
[272]	Conference	2014	Miser PS	Minimization of costs	Miser PS	Pump	Real Historical Data from Unnamed network (United Kingdom)
[262]	Journal	2019	MPC (non-explicit solver)	Minimization of costs	Equations	Pump Station	Synthetic Newtown
[54]	Journal	2023	Interior Point Line Search Algorithm	Maximization of Energy Production	Equations	Turbine, Valve	Synthetic Sicily (Italy)
[277]	Conference	2021	MPC solved with Gurobi and SCIP	Minimization of Costs	Equations	Pump	Synthetic NET1
[260]	Conference	2013	Mixed Integer Programming solved with COIN-OR	Minimization of Costs	Equations	Pump	Unclear
[247]	Conference	2018	DSS, with MPC	Minimization of Pollutants, Minimization of Costs, Pressure Control	EPANET, ANFYS, NN, FCM, ARIMA, SARIMA	Pump, Valve	Real Skiathos Island (Greece)
[254]	Journal	2022	MPC with NLP (Solved with IPOPT)	Minimization of costs, Pressure Control, Fire Control	Equations	Pump, Valve	Synthetic Bristol Water Field Lab (UK)
[278]	Journal	2022	MPC (solve with Dynamic Random Search), Feedback Type	Minimization of Costs, Pressure Control	EPANET	Pump	Real Sadra (Iran)

localization” had the fastest growth in the usage of ML techniques, underscoring a surge in importance in recent years. Numerous research works were also expected to implement hydraulic simulators using ML models, but such was not observed. ML models based on NN have also been growing exponentially in recent years in the WSS. With the mainstream use of DL approaches, a surge of new hydraulic simulators based on ML techniques is expected.

- **RQ3 - What are the limitations/challenges in the practical implementation of Smart Predictive Digital Twins in the WSS?** The main limitations of

implementing a Smart Predictive Digital Twin are twofold. First, a multi-use Digital Twin requires a robust communication system. Clearly, the communication infrastructure depends on the intended use, but for systems with multiple functions, the complexity of development increases dramatically. Second, there is some concern about allowing an autonomous system to control such a critical system directly. Not only from a technological standpoint but also potentially from a regulatory perspective. A push for new methodologies capable of assuring a regular control of WSS needs to be incentivized. In the literature, some works were found

that move towards securing control transmissions to the physical entity.

The contributions of this work are several-fold. As stated earlier, one of the main contributions is the exposure of the current state-of-the-art of the Digital Twin and related technologies as well as future trends of these topics. The approach allowed for an analysis of all pertinent fields of application, which in turn provides valuable insights into the needs and limitations, and allows for inferring future directions. Additionally, several research gaps were able to be identified, most notably the lack of ML for hydraulic simulators and the slow output of publications regarding control algorithms.

ANNEX

See Tables 6–17.

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